

**FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO CRIMES AND DEVIANT BEHAVIOURS
AMONG TEENAGERS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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Human Development and Family Studies.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this Dissertation was written by me and is a correct record of my own research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for any degree of this or any other university. All citations and sources of information are clearly acknowledged by means of reference.

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CERTIFICATION

This dissertation entitled “factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviours among teenagers in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government Area Lagos state, Nigeria is the outcome of the research carried out by ABE OPEYEMI ABIOLA in the Department of Home Science and Management, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta.

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ABSTRACT

The frequency of criminal activities and deviant conducts among teenagers worldwide has gained importance due to its impact on individuals and communities. Crimes are actions violating societal norms while deviant behaviours are acts that disrupt these norms. Socioeconomic status, parenting background, parenting styles, peer influence, school environment and social media exposure have been identified as major factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviours. This study therefore examined those factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviors among teenagers in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The research employed a cross-sectional research design. A multistage sampling procedure was adopted and a well-structured questionnaire was used to obtain data from selected 269 respondents. Results were analysed using PPMC, OLS, mean, frequency counts, percentage, standard deviation, Chi-Square, and Student t-test. Findings revealed that 52.0% of the respondents were female, Christians (63.9%) and a mean age of 17.6 years, most respondents were from monogamous families (63.9%) with 4-6 persons and their parents earned between ₦500,000 and ₦2,000,000 annually. Deviant behaviours reported by respondents varied from lying to adults (\bar{x} = 3.71) to petty theft (\bar{x} = 3.38) while criminal behaviours common among the respondents include being friends with well-known criminals (\bar{x} = 3.67) and knowing several people who have committed crimes (\bar{x} = 3.64). Based on the categorisation of behaviours as low (1.00-2.33), moderate (2.34-3.67) and high (3.68-5.00), it was found that respondents exhibited moderate criminal and deviant behaviours. Chi-square analysis revealed significant ($p < 0.05$) associations between household size ($\chi^2 = 158.08$, $df = 6$), annual income of parents ($\chi^2 = 127.77$, $df = 6$), fathers' education ($\chi^2 = 84.63$, $df = 10$), mothers' education ($\chi^2 = 90.18$, $df = 6$), mothers' occupation ($\chi^2 =$

82.67, $df = 8$) and deviant behaviours. There were also significant ($p < 0.05$) associations between class level ($\chi^2 = 73.44$, $df = 6$), household size ($\chi^2 = 96.54$, $df = 6$), annual income ($\chi^2 = 88.54$, $df = 6$), mothers' education ($\chi^2 = 112.48$, $df = 6$), fathers' occupation ($\chi^2 = 99.71$, $df = 8$), mothers' occupation ($\chi^2 = 70.39$, $df = 8$) and criminal behaviour. PPMC revealed significant ($p < 0.05$) relationships between school environment ($r = 0.42$), peer pressure ($r = 0.55$), social media usage ($r = 0.50$) and deviant behaviours. Significant ($p < 0.05$) relationships existed between school environment ($r = 0.57$), peer pressure ($r = 0.37$), social media usage ($r = 0.40$) and criminal behaviours. Student t-test revealed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in deviant behaviour exhibited by male and female respondents ($t = 2.96$) in favour of males. OLS analysis showed that overall independent variables contributed 72% ($R^2 = 0.72$) and 77% ($R^2 = 0.77$) to criminal and deviant behaviours respectively. In conclusion, the study found that most variables had significant associations with criminal and deviant behaviours. It is recommended that the Government and policymakers implement targeted interventions addressing socioeconomic gaps, bad school environments, parental education promoting effective parenting practices, peer support programs, and responsible digital use to foster positive teenage activities and discourage crimes and deviant behaviours in the study area.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this to Almighty God, the great potter in whose hand I am a clay and to the entire ABE family without whose support this programme would have been impossible.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

The frequency of criminal activity and deviant conducts among teenagers worldwide has gained importance in recent years. It continues to be a societal issue of concern because it impacts the lives of those involved and the community as a whole. The authority that families, schools and society have over teenagers who engage in deviant behaviours is gradually eroding. Though the use of authority to address these issues has not produced the desired results, a continued rise in youth engagement in deviant behaviours has far-reaching effects on families, communities and society.

Literature from previous research (Idris, 2016; Dada, 2017; Loveline & Jaja, 2020) show that youths are involved in criminal activity and aberrant behaviour which has an impact on how they act and will have long-term effects on individuals, their families and society as a whole. Studies on aggressive behaviour, hostility, school dropouts, substance misuse and criminality among teenagers in Africa are concerning. (Aute, 2019; Idris, 2016; Dada 2017; Loveline & Jaja, 2020). Another investigation carried out in Nigeria revealed a rise in criminal activity and deviant behaviour among teenagers, which was linked to a lack of discipline and moral decay among the youth (Idris, 2016).

According to Wachukwu & Ibegunam (2012), antisocial behaviour, personality disorder, or conduct disorder (terms associated with delinquency) are crimes committed by youths under the age of nineteen that are typically characterized as violations of established societal norms and values. It appears that children are

becoming involved in crimes that are typically perpetrated by adults who are older than nineteen (19) years.

In industrialised nations, there has also been a notable rise in violent juvenile crime. Maybe as a result of the growing economic difficulty and crisis that many sections of the continent are experiencing, Africa has not been an exception to the rising rates of youth violence. Juvenile delinquency is a serious concern in Nigeria, where reports of everyday economic difficulties are received. Arson, drug abuse, rape, malpractice, school crime, intimidation, cultism, truancy, school dropouts, lying, deceit, stealing, callousness, fighting, bullying, unwanted pregnancy, examination malpractices, lack of respect for elders, alcoholism and running away from homes and prostitution are other examples of common anti-social behaviour in Nigeria (Wachukwu & Ibegbunam, 2012; Olaniyi, 2018). Until steps are taken to stem the rise of juvenile crime, there is no chance that Nigeria will ever see an enhanced, more robust and stable criminal culture (Sanni, *et al.*, 2010). In Nigeria, juvenile delinquency is viewed as a significant issue that seriously impedes the nation's progress (Mohammed, *et al.*, 2009).

Adegoke (2015) stated that one of the Nigeria Police Force's three primary areas of concern in 2010 was the involvement of young people in criminal activity. According to his report, common juvenile offences including robberies, burglaries, riots and theft are the most prevalent in Nigeria. According to the report, 19,000 Nigerian teenagers received prison sentences in 2001 for committing over 185,000 crimes. Also 31% of young people arrested in Nigeria in 2005 were found to have committed shoplifting; 17% had committed robbery; and 11% had engaged in rioting. In 2015, these rose to roughly 38% shop theft, 21% robbery and 13% rioting.

With over 20 million residents, Lagos is the most populated and urbanised state in Nigeria (Ojo & Aghedo, 2013; Ojo & Ojewale, 2019) and one of the most populated and vibrant cities in Africa, offering a setting with a variety of opportunities, cultural influences and socioeconomic differences. These elements' interactions can significantly affect impressionable young minds, sometimes with unfavourable results.

Numerous theories – the Differential Association theory by E. H Sutherland in 1939, the Strain theory by R. K Melton in 1962, the General theory of crime by M. R Gottfredson & T. Hirschi in 1990 and so on - have been put forth to explain why teenagers act in ways that are out of character. According to some theories, adolescents may exhibit deviant behaviours as a sign of maturity or as a step toward adulthood (Farrington, 2017). Some hypothesised that the conduct stems from heightened self-obsession and an urge to become aware (Price, 2017). Nonetheless, most theories contend that social and environmental elements including family, peers, school, community and cultural belief systems cause deviant behaviour (Hong & Espelage, 2012). These are the family's socioeconomic status, parenting styles and community elements like the media, peer pressure and the school environment.

The socioeconomic characteristics of a family significantly impact a child's development and behaviour. According to West & Farmington (1973) as cited in Omboto, *et al.*, (2013), large family size and low income are common traits among young offenders. Every parent wants to do the best for their kids, which includes attending to their needs completely, supporting them physically and emotionally and building a strong bond with them. These would guarantee that the kids develop into self-sufficient, responsible adults who can live in harmony with their community

(Aute, *et al.*, 2020). However, when a person's income or expenses fall below the poverty line, they are deemed to be living in poverty (Uyang, *et al.*, 2016) with financial limitations that have terrible consequences that could permeate the parent-child bond and subsequently influence the conduct of the kids.

Parenting styles, the act of parenthood, the child's upbringing, training rearing, or child education adopted by the parents also shape adolescent behaviour. Uye, *et al.*, (2023) cite strict discipline, parental disagreement, rejection, and inadequate involvement in a child's activities as possible contributors to delinquency.

Beyond family, the school environment plays a crucial role. Education is widely recognized as a powerful tool for imparting knowledge, positive values, and desirable behaviour to pupils. Students form bonds with both their teachers and peers while they are in school. Strong relationships that support the formation of good character can be fostered by the type of relationship that occurs between students and their teachers. Due to the degree of closeness that exists between students and the other people they deal with at school, they may engage in criminal and deviant behaviours or not engage (Asiyai, 2019).

Studies by Blakemore & Mills (2014) and Miller (2010) indicated that peer pressure plays a role in teens' decisions to engage in risky behaviours. According to Blakemore & Mills (2014), at this developmental stage, teens are particularly receptive to social cues from their social settings, which may account for the significant influence of social approval on a great deal of their behaviour. Due to the belief that social conformity is a prerequisite for social popularity, early and middle adolescents are more vulnerable to peer pressure as they want to gain the social approval and conformity of their peers (Laursen & Veenstra, 2021). According to Barnert *et al.*

(2015), peer pressure and defiance of parental control might lead to youth involvement in criminal activities.

Social media usage through visits to platforms to locate and connect to other users; create restricted or semi-public profiles within a closed system; and view and navigate the list of connections made by other users within the system (Saiphoo & Vahedi, 2023) could profoundly affect behavioural patterns. Social media sites are believed to significantly influence users' social behavioural patterns (Abdullah, *et al.*, 2009).

By understanding the societal influences and consequences of teenage crimes, society can create focused and successful interventions that support positive youth development, lower risk factors, reroute young lives toward positive paths, and create a supportive environment for adolescents. Everyone can live in a safer and more prosperous society if teenagers are given the tools they need to make wise decisions and feel like they belong in their communities.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Crime and deviant behaviours pose a threat to a country's political, social and economic security and are a major contributing factor to underdevelopment because they undermine democracy, the rule of law and the nation's capacity to foster development because it discourages both local and foreign investments. They also lower the quality of life, destroy human and social capital and sour relations between citizens and the state. Nigeria, one of the world's developing nations, is dealing with an increase in crime rates, criminal intent and varying degrees of delinquency. Even though juvenile delinquency is a long-standing issue, it appears that crimes and juvenile delinquency from the past cannot be compared to those in the present.

In recent times, antisocial behaviours linked to teenage delinquents have included cybercrimes (such as Yahoo - yahoo), drug-related offences, violence, carrying a weapon, alcohol abuse, rape, examination malpractice, armed robbery, murder, bullying of both peers and teachers, cultism, truancy, school dropouts and other illicit activities. Naturally, the hope of a better, safer and more prosperous Nigerian society will remain unattainable unless action is taken to curb the tide of teenage delinquency. The frequency of these crimes is increasing with no significant actions regarding stemming the possible long-term repercussions for both the affected individuals and society at large.

Therefore, this study investigated and identified the causes of teenagers' tendency for criminal and deviant behaviours in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government, Lagos, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The broad objective of this study was to assess factors contributing to crimes or deviant behaviours of teenagers in Public Secondary Schools in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives were to:

1. Describe the socio-personal characteristics of respondents in the study area;
2. Evaluate the relationship between variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviours and criminal and deviant behaviours of the respondents;
3. Assess the level of contribution by independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents;
4. Differentiate criminal and deviant behaviour exhibited by male and female respondents.

1.4 Research questions

1. What is the association between socio-personal characteristics of respondents and criminal and deviant behaviours?
2. What is the relationship between the variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviour and criminal and deviant behaviour of the respondents?
3. What is the contribution of overall independent variables to crimes and deviant behaviours of the respondents?
4. What is the difference in criminal and deviant behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents?

1.5 Hypotheses of the study

Ho1: there is no significant association between the socio-personal characteristics of the respondents and criminal and deviant behaviour of the respondents.

Ho2: there is no significant relationship between the variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviours and the criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents.

Ho3: there is no significant contribution by overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the criminal and deviant behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents.

1.6 Justification of the Study

Considering the menace which criminal and deviant behaviour has caused in the recent past in society (Cioban, *et al.*, 2021; Dullas, *et al.*, 2021), it became important to identify factors that contribute to its sustenance, especially among teenagers. Knowledge of the role of home (socioeconomic status and parenting style) and societal (school environment, peer pressure and social media) factors in teenage

criminal and deviant behaviour could lead parents to adopting a holistic approach to rearing children. Identifying the factors that contribute to delinquency within the school environment would benefit stakeholders in the educational system such as students, teachers, counsellors, administrators and policymakers in addressing risk factors within its system. To the teenagers, the findings of this study would enable them to identify what is considered a crime, what is considered deviant behaviour, risk factors of such behaviours and the possible consequences. The outcome of this study would assist the government, policymakers and society at large, know that they are there not only to build protective forces, offset these antisocial behaviour at the onset but also the need to provide necessary facilities and improved ways of life to deter or discourage teenagers from engaging in such behaviours.

1.7 Operational definition of terms

Criminal behaviour: refers to adolescent behaviour that sets them up to commit a crime such as rape, armed robbery, kidnapping, arson etc. When there is a purpose, a means, and an opportunity, an unlawful act takes place.

Deviant behaviour: refers to behaviour that deviates from social norms such as cyberbullying, truancy, alcoholism, petty theft etc. which might include formal laws and cultural standards as well as unofficial social regulations.

Peer pressure: refers to the feeling of uneasiness experienced by teenagers which is caused by pressures from social and significant others around.

School environment: refers to the extent to which a school environment is adequate or inadequate in terms of resources that support students' learning.

Parenting style: refers to the ways that parents use to bring up their children, as well as the discipline and home training techniques they employ to enforce their expectations on that person, particularly from childhood to adulthood.

Socio-economic status: is the class or social status of a person or group.

Social media use: refers to the application of digital technology that enables the sharing of concepts and data over virtual networks, including text and images.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of crimes or Criminal behaviour

Deviant behaviour and criminal behaviour are two different but related categories, according to Goode (2019). Since criminal and deviant activity share many conceptual and logical similarities, it is difficult to discern between the two. Both deviance and criminal behaviour constitute an array of behaviours and actions; but, as one might expect, deviance is much more varied than crime, incorporating conditions and attitudes as well as behaviour (Goode, 2019).

According to Okolie-Osemene & Ukoji (2016), one of the main dangers to human security worldwide is crime. Crime has always been a global issue with a societal component. Whether we like it or not, crime will always be a part of life. Although crime is widespread globally and not restricted to any one area, the extent of crime differs amongst societies because no society is immune to it (Pieszko, 2016; Harrison, Ratcliffe, *et al.*, 2014). Each country on earth has its distinctive laws that contravene ethical and moral standards because of its own cultures and communities.

Criminal activity, often known as crime, is defined as an action that defies established laws or social standards and requires the involvement of the state to be punished or sanctioned. Khan *et al.* (2019) define crime as any behaviour that seem to go against the existing legal framework of a state. Every crime requires a determined criminal, a suitable target, and the absence of anything or someone who may function as a protector (Khan *et al.*, 2019). According to Ejemeyovwi (2015), a crime can only occur if victims, offenders, and possessions are present in a particular location within a specified period.

Crime can occur on land, in the air, or at sea. Civilisation is especially concerned about the rise in maritime theft and piracy (World Bank Group, 2020). "The circumstances surrounding crime in Nigeria disregards all forms of social stratification in the society, as both the high (haves) and low (have-nots) experienced the effects of crimes," according to Balogun, *et al.*, (2014).

While some scholars, such as Edwin Sutherland, believe that criminal behaviour is learnt, Cesare Lombroso (1911), cited by Silver & Silver (2022), relates crime to biological anomalies. Sociology attributes a crime to inadequate integration in society, while psychology attributes crime to psychological and genetic criminal features (Merton, 2017).

2.2 Types of crimes or criminal behaviour

Since most crimes are divided into a few main classifications by criminologists, there are many distinct types of crimes. The primary categories of crimes in society, according to Vijayarani *et al.*, (2020), include cybercrimes, statutory crimes, inchoate crimes, property crimes, and personal crimes. Crimes against people, property, lawful authority, and local acts are among the categories of crimes listed by Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (Crime Statistics, 2018). Sowmyya (2015) made a distinction between several types of crime, according to the media that is impacted. He lists several sorts of crimes, including organised, victimless, cyber, public safety, white-collar, personal, and property crimes. These offences are closely related to the classification of crimes used by the National Incident-Based Reporting System (NIBRS) in the United States.

The NIBRS divided crimes into three categories: crimes against society, which included drug offences and narcotics violations; crimes against individuals, which

included assault, rape, and homicide; and crimes against property, which included robbery, arson, and property destruction. Crimes are generally classified into several categories, including crimes against individuals, crimes against property, and others. As to the findings of Jonathan *et al.*, (2021), all kinds of crime has an effect on the socioeconomic activities of individuals as well as the social cohesiveness of a society.

2.3 Consequences of crimes or criminal behaviour

Individual

- Given that a significant percentage of juvenile antisocial behaviour develops into adult criminal activity, legal consequences may lead to incarceration or a criminal record (Hanrahan, 2014).
- Challenges with employment: Persistent offenders may have trouble reintegrating into society even when they are involved, which could lead to unemployment in the future (Williams, 2012).

Society

- According to Dinisman & Moroz (2017), there are several negative effects of crime on a victim's emotional, physical, and financial health. Those with post-traumatic stress disorder are more likely to have both short- and long-term emotional and psychological issues, including a higher risk of suicide, as a result of the psychological and emotional fallout from violent crimes (Jackson & Gouseti, 2015).
- The cost of repairing various forms of damage caused by crime, the loss of revenue used for prison maintenance and rehabilitation, and the exorbitant funds set aside for the capture, investigation, and prosecution of criminals will be covered by funds that should otherwise have been allocated for the provision of basic amenities (Jeke, *et al.*, 2021).

Impact on relationship

- family stress: Wickliffe (2012) states that having a criminal record has the adverse consequence of keeping criminals from getting essential support and care from their relatives.
- According to Singer & Slovak (2016), a family member of an offender may experience psychological stress for the rest of their life. Most parents may be forced to move out of their community due to the abnormal behaviour of their ward, which leaves a psychological scar.

Economic

- In the words of Sundaram *et al.* (2016), criminal conduct undermines a nation's economy, increasing the cost of upholding the law, and eventually causing both large and small businesses to close.
- Folorunsho and Rufus (2017) argued that the rate of crime has an impact on company entry, indicating that an increase in crime would lower businessmen's activities and ultimately negatively impact a nation's economic activities.

2.4 Concept of Deviant Behaviour

According to Saldana (2013), every culture has a set of established customs, laws, and regulations that are expected to be adhered to by every member of the community. Since deviant behaviour spans a wide range of social strata, it is characterised differently in every culture and community. Deviance can be observed in social reactions among groups as well as in the behaviour itself. Deviant conduct is defined by sociologists as "behaviours, acts, and beliefs that contravene significant social

norms and generate or are likely to generate condemnation, stigma, social isolation, condemnation, and/or punishment by relevant audiences" (Goode, 2015).

Any conduct that deviates from the accepted norms of a society or group is considered deviant behaviour; these behaviours are typically viewed as going against societal norms and values (Bolu-Steve & Esere, 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2018). According to Suleiman (2011), deviant behaviour is characterised by three things: behaviours that make it difficult for a person to function in society, behaviours that keep a person from meeting their own needs, and behaviours that harm the well-being of the general public. Since certain people would never follow the rules, there will always be some deviants in any society (Fatoki & Kobiowu, 2020). According to Bicchieri *et al.*, (2018), those who stray from societal norms to follow their interests typically receive less support from the community.

This means that partnering to interact with these people may be able to interrupt the pattern of individualistic, self-centred behaviour. A man's actions that land him in jail could make another guy a saint because the quality of an act depends on the environment in which it is performed and the attitude of the audience.

2.5 Types of deviant behaviour

- 1) Substance abuse and drug usage: It has been noted that youngsters, both within and outside of schools, abuse alcohol, smoke cigarettes, and use heroin, Indian hemp, and other drugs not recommended by doctors (Pauji, 2022).
- 2) The array of sexual misbehaviour activities that students participate in, including lesbianism, abortion, premarital sex, masturbation, and homosexuality, is referred to as sexual deviancy (Mogbana, & Edward, 2022).

- 3) Cyber deviancy: Yar & Steinmetz (2019) define cybercrime as a broad spectrum of unlawful acts leveraging information and communication technologies. Because of this, harmful online behaviour that is sanctioned by law is known as cybercrime.

The various forms of disruptive online activities are included in the general term "cyber deviance," which refers to informal legal transgressions (Jewkes & Yar, 2013; Graham & Smith, 2019; Yar & Steinmetz, 2019). Cyberbullying (Hinduja & Patchin, 2010; Holt, Bossler & May 2012); digital piracy (Udris, 2016); online harassment and computer hacking (Lee, 2018); sexting and exposure to pornographic content on the internet (Karaian, 2012; Garcia-Gomez, 2017; Dodaj *et al.*, 2020). Adolescents who defy societal norms, beliefs, or principles sometimes engage in deviant behaviours such as cultism, stealing, vandalism, aggressive behaviour, bullying, and indecent attire.

2.6 Consequences of deviant behaviour

Individual

Unsatisfactory academic results, social disrepute, rejection, or separation from peers (Akilandeswari & Annalakshmi, 2023), school abandonment (Ali, *et al.*, 2014), increased involvement in criminal activity (Ubangha, *et al.*, 2013), disturbances in the educational process (Dalhatu & Yunusa, 2013; Hayden, 2011). Aute (2019) further mentioned that deviation sometimes leads to death or health problems.

2.7 Concept of Teens, teenage crimes and juvenile delinquency

Teenagers are at a stage of life that many people find difficult for students. They go through mental, physical, and emotional changes, which they have to understand in light of the social setting in which they live.

The World Health Organisation (2013) claims that not enough empirical evidence exists to support the classification of the adolescent stage as hazardous. During this phase of transition, teens frequently act in ways that are considered antisocial by society as a whole. Thus, notions of the teenage or adolescent stage must be taken into consideration. Researchers are unable to come up with a consensus definition because of the unique differences in physical, emotional, and cognitive maturation that teenagers encounter.

According to estimates, about 1.8 billion people on the planet are between the ages of 10 and 24. This statistic includes teenagers. Juvenile misbehaviour and criminality are viewed as dangers to the peace that citizens of the country or community enjoy (Bernburg, 2019). This is a worldwide issue that cannot be avoided in any society with a set standard of living (Antwi, 2016).

According to Walsh *et al.*, (2020), status offences comprise behaviours such as running away from home, driving without a licence, smoking, vandalism, underage drinking, skipping school, ganging, and running away from home. Lateness, rudeness, absenteeism, thieving, lying, and vandalism are all associated with immature age factors, according to a 2015 study by Ojo.

In many societies today, there is a growing prevalence of crimes like as rape, drug abuse, verbal abuse, thuggery, sexual promiscuity, theft, fraud, gangsterism, bullying, robbery, cultism, drug usage, and even killing by teenagers (Yusuf *et al.*, 2021). It is impossible to isolate the problem of juvenile criminality from Okon's (2017) findings regarding drug addiction, prostitution, abortion, exam malpractice, truancy, theft, and fraud.

The fact that children and adolescents have not lived up to certain social standards has drawn the attention of many people who are worried about how children are developing. Since many young people have recently given up on their schooling in quest of illusory independence, support, and power, the harmful effects of youthful criminality cannot be underestimated.

2.8 Factors contributing to crime and deviant behaviour

Several variables predispose youth to participate in criminal and deviant behaviours. These elements can be classified into three broad categories: home-based, school-based, and societal. Divorce, polygamy, poverty, and inadequate parental care and training are examples of home-based risk factors. School-based factors include a lack of discipline among staff and pupils, peer group influence, and a lack of dedication from teachers. Finally, society-based factors include corruption, political indiscipline, and moral degeneration.

The study of crimes and deviant behaviour cannot be viewed as a singular phenomenon; rather, it must be examined with other factors like religiosity (Adamczyk, *et al.*, 2017), family dynamics and influence, including parental communication (Roisko, *et al.*, 2014), parental styles (Ruiz-Hernández, *et al.*, 2019), peer influence (Leung, *et al.*, 2014), parental imprisonment (Abdullah & Rahman, 2016), animal cruelty (Longobardi & Badenes-Ribera, 2019), victimisation and sexual victimisation (McGrath, *et al.*, 2011; Dennis *et al.*, 2012; Engström, 2021), maltreatment of children (Fitton & Fazel, 2020), and non-emotional callousness and impulsivity (Toro, *et al.*, 2020), family collapse, absence of parental oversight, monitoring, and financial difficulties (Nisar, *et al.*, 2015). According to Kinanee (2011), home-based factors including poverty, polygamy, and divorce were more

frequently cited as significant contributors to deviant conduct in teenagers. According to a study by Arthur *et al.* (2002), risk variables tend to rise with age during teenage development, and this relationship between risk factor exposure and adolescent delinquency was confirmed. Connors *et al.*, (2004) agreed that more than one risk factor usually contributes to antisocial behaviour.

Socioeconomic status as a risk factor

According to earlier research by Aute *et al.*, (2020), Machebe & Ifelunni (2014), Sariaslan *et al.*, (2014), and Stalmach *et al.*, (2014), a family's socioeconomic status has a significant effect on the tendency of a teenager to criminal and deviant behaviours. Socioeconomic status is the term used to describe the socio-environmental factors that indicate the condition in which an individual or a family lives. These factors include household size, parents' literacy level, household income, the presence of both parents, and whether or not the parent is working (Nezhad, *et al.*, 2012). This suggests that having two parents, a full-time job, a higher level of parent education, and a higher household income could all be associated with having a higher socioeconomic position, and the reverse would be true for a lower socioeconomic status. It was once said by Alain Peyrefitte that "poverty is the mother of crime." When an individual's measurable standard of living, as determined by their income or expenses, falls below the poverty line, they are deemed to be impoverished (Uyang *et al.*, 2016). Because of the extreme poverty in the nation, 39.1% of Nigerians, according to a UNDP-OPHI report from 2022, struggle to meet their basic needs. As a result, it is difficult for parents to raise their children consistently and positively because they lack opportunities and social support, which can have detrimental effects on the parent-child relationship and ultimately have an impact on the children. In the words of Owusu (2016), there exists a strong correlation between

socioeconomic status and crime, meaning that people who grow up in impoverished environments with low-income families, substandard housing, and high unemployment rates are more likely to commit crimes. Also, fear of crime and crime itself are not equally distributed over space. Savolainen, *et al.*, (2013) provided evidence to support this viewpoint by stating that there is a direct correlation between poverty and crime in society. The relationship between poor socioeconomic position and crime is complicated and difficult to study since poverty is frequently linked to criminal activity (Sharkey, *et al.*, 2017).

Individual risk factor

A person may end up in jail if they rebel against pro-social norms and ideals and exhibit delinquent conduct when they are young. Teenagers who act antisocially are predisposed to do so by a few personal characteristics. Some people offend for physiological or psychological reasons, claims Durrant (2018). Studies on human conduct have revealed psychological risk factors such as fixation with guns, behavioural problems, and violent outbursts (Pinquart, 2017). According to a report by Farrington *et al.*, (2012), alcohol usage is associated with juvenile delinquency since it has been demonstrated to negatively affect an individual's psychological functioning. Aggression, lying, disobedience, thievery, destructiveness, and a lack of self-control are examples of other individual risk factors. Swanston *et al.*, (2003) identified sexual abuse as an independent risk factor for aberrant conduct.

2.8.1 Social and Environmental Factors

Community as a Risk Factor

It is common to use the terms "community" and "society" interchangeably. It describes a social community bound by common principles, interests, and geographic boundaries, according to Cindi (2006). Adolescent misbehaviour and antisocial behaviour in the community are related; as the phrase goes, "children are a mirror of their community." A society is likely to have a higher crime rate than another if it has a greater proportion of low-income, unemployed, and impoverished citizens. A nation's degree of education, high-density housing, congestion, and a diverse racial and cultural mix are among the many elements that are deemed criminogenic. (Muhammadi *et al.*, 2022).

When Prinsloo (2007) asserts that modern materialism is a major factor in society's moral decline, which influences adolescent behaviour, he makes a valid observation. Because this phenomenon makes the person obsessed with their fulfilment and enrichment, it puts them at risk of offending others. Stewart & Simons (2010) claim that the community acts as a "tool-kit" for a range of antisocial behaviours, especially in impoverished places. Antisocial activity eventually becomes the norm and is sometimes viewed as normal in some civilisations.

Risk factors within the school

Many individuals believe that education is a useful tool for giving pupils the values, information, and abilities they need to exhibit desired behaviour. Parents send their children to school not just to instil moral principles but also to provide them with the skills and information needed to make the best possible impacts on the growth of both their own and their community. According to Osaat (2012), education may be seen as

a means of fostering and transmitting a person's culture from one generation to the next, with the ultimate objective being the realisation of a dignified life and manner of living for every individual. This suggests that education is a means by which the young inherit the cultural and moral ideals of their elders.

The school environment is the second most important place for teenagers' social development. There, they learn relevant subjects and develop skills that support their transition into adulthood. They learn social ideals and proper behaviour from their cultures as a reaction to the demands of social conformity. The institution aims to uphold and further social norms. However, certain negative attitudes exist regarding education, including those related to insufficient finance, poor management, limited opportunities for socialisation, and messy facilities. Masitsa (2011) asserts that high standards, professional and caring teacher conduct, a supportive learning environment, good discipline procedures, and strong school management and governance capabilities are all characteristics of successful schools that serve as a deterrent to crime and deviant behaviour in the school setting.

Adolescents with a propensity for crime are more likely to perpetrate it in an unorganised and chaotic learning environment. When the school fails to properly express and promote its ideals through its code of conduct, and when teachers fail to model and uphold these same values, children become antisocial because they lack direction.

In Lagos state secondary schools, there was a notable amount of student misconduct, according to Ali *et al.*, (2014). Students' poor performance in external exams was attributed to administrative misconduct by principals, a lack of infrastructure, and indiscipline (Mbaabu & Orodho, 2014). Cheng (2012) established a connection

between the aberrant behaviour of students and the school environment and relationships within it. Yaman & Uygumada (2009) claim that when a classroom is packed, teachers tend to use passive learning techniques, which serve as a haven for disruptive activity. Khumalo (2019), referencing a past study by De Wet (2003), claimed that one of the reasons why teenage misbehaviour occurs in schools is because of insufficient school leadership. Schools in impoverished areas lack time, space, and enough staff members—all of which are necessary to provide a compassionate learning environment. An impersonal environment is produced when teachers are overworked and overbooked, which limits the appropriate interaction that should occur between teachers and pupils (Mufannechiya, 2011).

Truancy and Absenteeism

A social force that shapes children's habits, interests, attitudes, and sentiments while passing down cultural norms, values, and traditions from one generation to the next is the school. Even though truancy and attendance concerns are grave challenges for our schools, the detrimental effects on pupils have received little attention. Schools are institutions that provide morals and discipline to their students.

Truancy, as defined by Gullatt & Lemoine in Musa (2014), can be summed up as a behaviour in which kids choose not to attend class because they can engage in other, more fulfilling activities outside school while Fuglemann & Richardson (2011) defined truancy as a deliberate absence from school without a legitimate reason, independent of the parent or guardian's knowledge or consent. Absenteeism is the term used to describe students who miss school frequently. According to Musa (2014), a truant either leaves school entirely or shows up late to engage in extracurricular activities that attract his interest.

Four types of truants identified by Adubea (2020), citing Owodunni (1996) are:

- Internal truants: Students who attend school but miss specific classes, often wandering around the campus or engaging in non-academic activities;
- In-school truants: Students who attend school but are not in their assigned classrooms, often hiding in other areas or pretending to be in a different class;
- Home-based truants: Students who attend school sporadically, often staying home without permission or valid reasons;
- Psychological truants: Students who skip classes because they hate the teacher or the subject.

Truancy and absenteeism are signs of maladjustment that require psychological intervention (Ibili, 2022). Students who are absent from school may take up deviant activities like exam cheating, rape, theft, drug addiction, smoking, cybercrime, and tardiness. It is an act of indiscipline that has been creating misunderstandings among teenagers, teachers, parents, and society (Oni, 2010).

Peer group (Rejection & Association) as a risk factor

Peer groups are defined as small groups of people who are particularly related to one another, whether in their profession, at school, or in society, and who share a shared position, age, or educational background. A small group of people who are the same age and who share activities could potentially be used to characterise it (Zaki *et al.*, 2014). In addition to highlighting the importance of peer games in socialisation, peer group studies show the connection between unfavourable peer connections throughout childhood and later socially unacceptable behaviour. The impact that others receive

from their peers affects their thoughts, communication styles, behaviours, interpersonal connections, and even their attire is known as peer pressure.

Peer pressure, as defined by Jones (2010), is the power of individuals in the same social class or age group to persuade a person in that age group to do or act in ways that they otherwise would not. Peer pressure can be accomplished through two different methods: peer coercion, which is the use of peer pressure to intimidate someone into acting out of fear or anxiety, or peer contagion, which is the mutual influence process between an individual and a peer that involves behaviours and emotions that might adversely affect one's development or cause harm to others (Kurtz & Zavala, 2017).

Adolescent risk-taking behaviours, such as criminality, drug misuse, skipping classes, stealing, cheating, damaging public property, abusing drugs or alcohol, and engaging in sexual activity, are typically associated with peer pressure (Arief & Martins, 2011). Teenagers between the ages of 16 and 18 are more influenced by their peers than those in other age groups, according to a 2017 study by Deepika & Prema. Some of the social vices that are common among teens in Nigeria and in society at large have been attributed to peer group influence.

Adolescents' sexuality and career choices are only two domains of life where social influence has been demonstrated to have an impact (Kim *et al.*, 2010). During this period of development, peer influence may even outweigh parental influence (Berndt, 2018).

As to the findings of Matthews *et al.*, (2015), an individual's probability of engaging in deviant and antisocial behaviour escalates if they encounter social rejection from their peers at this developmental stage. Teenagers who were exposed to drug users

succumbed to peer pressure and the seductiveness of drug use. Peer pressure is a major factor in drug addiction among students (Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2010). Response to peers can also determine the significant and unique role they play in our lives. Positive or negative, peer pressure has been shown to have an impact on teenagers. For example, research from Landau (2002), cited in Mosha (2017), shows that teens who form positive peer groups put forth more effort when learning and participating in social activities. They also show a fear of engaging in delinquent activities, which results in a marked increase in academic achievement, voluntary charity, participation in sports and other productive endeavours, etc. (De Guzman, 2007; Kellie, 2013 cited in Mosha, 2017; Véronneau & Dishion, 2011). However, in 2017 Deepika & Prema said the negative influence of peer pressure is greater than positive influence.

2.8.2 Family Factor

Parenting style as a risk factor

Parents are a child's first teachers, so they have to provide them with their first education in the physical, mental, religious, and emotional domains as well as in cooperation, courtesy, tolerance, and respect for authority figures. Thus, when their kids grow up to be teenagers in society, the influence parents have on them becomes apparent in their own lives. From birth to adulthood, parenting is the act of nurturing and supporting a child's intellectual, emotional, and physical growth (Amin & Eliasa, 2023). The way that parents interact with their children may play a role in the children's deviant behaviour. Parental rejection, aggressive parent-child interactions, and other unpleasant events are all necessary conditions for the use of parenting intervention analysis (Biglan, *et al.*, 2012). Different parenting techniques or styles can be seen in the roles that parents play; they include Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive, and Uninvolved, which describe how parents manage their children's

upbringing by their values, beliefs, and cultural background (Yakubu, 2018). According to Abdul Gafor and Kurukkan (2014), two primary factors influence a parent's behaviour: their attentiveness as a parent and their demandingness. Parental demandingness refers to the demands parents make on their children to become integrated into the family through their demands, supervision, disciplinary efforts, and willingness to confront the disobedient child. At the same time, parental responsiveness refers to the degree to which parents intentionally foster individuality, self-regulation, and self-assertion by being aware of, supportive of, and obedient to children's needs and demands (Baumrind, 1971 cited in Abdul Gafor & Kurukkan, 2014).

Table 1: Parenting topologies

	High demandingness	Low demandingness
High responsiveness	Authoritative	Permissive
Low responsiveness	Authoritarian	Uninvolved

Authoritarian parenting style

Authoritarian parenting is characterised by rigid, traditional parenting that emphasises obedience and conformity and demands that rules be followed without question in a less friendly setting. Authoritarian parents are known for being unresponsive but for being extremely demanding. Authoritarian parents also engage in strong control, restrict open communication, and show low levels of trust and engagement towards their kids. Strong methods that are most frequently used against authoritarian-distinctive, coercive, power-assertive behaviours include verbal hostility and psychological control (Maccoby & Martins, 1983; Baumrind, Larzelere, & Owens quoted in Hoskins, 2014). It consists of strict rules, strict parenting, severe discipline, and a lack of a nurturing environment for children, all of which lead to improper behaviour and aggressive behaviours in children (McNamara, *et al.*, 2010). Authoritarian parents are not only demanding and status-driven, but they also don't listen to their kids' needs and provide a disciplined environment with explicit rules. Parents who feel that their child should follow their instructions blindly use a "do as you are told" approach to discipline and discourage verbal dialogue or compromise, according to Simons *et al.*, (2007). Instead of educating their kids on how to make better decisions, authoritarian parents are more interested in using punishment to make their kids feel terrible about their failures. All members of the family become violent when the parents employ coercive methods that don't work (Crosswhite & Kerpelman, 2009). Teens who experience rejection and hostility from their parents become more irrational and agitated, which increases the likelihood that they may engage in antisocial behaviour.

Authoritative parenting style

Authoritative parents are highly responsive, and demanding, and show more supporting behaviours than harsh ones. They also promote psychological compromise, explain the rationale behind rules, and reinforce goals through the use of reason, power, and shape. It is commonly known that beneficial teenage development is fostered by authoritative parenting and that adolescents who have authoritative parents are less likely to engage in externalising behaviours (Hoskins, 2014). With its participatory leadership style, this parenting approach encourages the presentation of a positive self-concept, honesty, responsibility, and acceptance of oneself. Charles, (2018) and Hoskins (2014) reported that this parenting approach is the most beneficial and effective way to raise children with positive adolescent outcomes, providing strong behavioural supervision and a great degree of emotional support in a home environment. They maintain control by encouraging their children to follow social norms, keeping an eye on their actions, and setting and upholding clear expectations for behaviour. The characteristics of authoritative parents include having a positive, optimistic attitude, confidence in one's ability to finish tasks, skilful emotion regulation, and developed social skills, according to Maccoby & Martin in Louis (2022). With appropriate communication that is devoid of judgement or condemnation, the child receives direction from authoritative parents on how to be their best self. Authoritative parents invest a great deal of time and energy in preventing behavioural problems before enforcing constructive discipline methods (Maria & Nwadiuso, 2017).

Permissive Parenting style

A potentially detrimental, unfavourable, and disastrous parenting style is permissive or laissez-faire. High levels of responsiveness and low levels of demandingness, a lack of rules and consequences for disobedience, a lack of involvement in parenting, and an emotional lack of empathy are all characteristics of permissive parenting (Johnson, 2016).

Permissive parents, according to Utti (2006), have no clear objectives, raise their kids passively, and are generally forgiving because they prefer to avoid conflict. They also act in a way that validates their adolescent child's impulses, desires, and behaviour while involving them in family decision-making. The parent treats their wards as equals, exercise minimal control over them, rarely impose rules, and place more importance on their friendship and affection of their teenager rather than giving them structure and discipline. Rather than providing education and guidance, parents allow their children to make their own choices and set their guidelines (e.g., when to come home at night, who they date or socialise with, and what they eat and drink) (Menkiti, 2019). The characteristics of permissive parenting include impaired emotional regulation, disruptive attitude, low stamina for difficult activities, and rebellious and belligerent behaviour when faced with challenges." They may participate in more violent and antisocial behaviours because of their child's limited moral development and lack of respect for authority figures and rules. As a result, when their children reach adolescence and begin acting more outwardly, they also show a sharp decline in monitoring (Capuzzi & Stauffer, 2016).

Neglectful / Uninvolved parenting lifestyle

Compared to the other three parenting philosophies, neglectful parents may have the lowest expectations, which makes them the most detrimental and destructive to the outcomes of their adolescents. It is characterised by low responsiveness and low demandingness, with parents frequently neglecting to keep an eye on or oversee their child's behaviour and failing to encourage or assist the development of self-regulation in their child. Generally speaking, these parents are perceived as being disengaged from their child-rearing duties and uninvolved with their children's needs (Hoeve *et al.*, 2009).

Of the four parenting methods of thought, the uninvolved approach produced the majority of single and divorced parents and was believed to have the worst effect on teenage outcomes (Johnson, 2016). The neglecting approach is thought to be the most effective at creating risk factors for children who engage in deviant behaviours because it lacks structure and control with their adolescents and frequently results in a lack of closeness between parents and children (Hoeve *et al.*, 2009). Parents who do not participate in their children's day-to-day activities do not supervise or support their behaviour. These parents interact with the public very little to non-existent, showing a lack of concern for the needs, whereabouts, the experiences of their teenagers with friends or at school, they are too engrossed with their personal affairs. Louis (2022) states that these parents are neither overbearing nor forgiving. The saying "children should be seen but not heard" may apply in this situation. Occasionally, the child is left to fend for himself in a family with little to no structure. Unless the child's behaviours drag the parent or family into disrepute, parents and children never address moral issues and the parent avoids involvement in the child's life. Then, the child's parents would most likely either shield him by claiming he was

a victim of other people's acts or ban him from entering the family. Teens reared in this way, according to Steinberg, 2001 in Pinquart (2017), are more likely to suffer from behavioural disorders and are not exposed to nearly any type of parenting, which lowers their psychological well-being and increases their rates of substance usage.

2.8.3 Psychological Factors

Lack of Empathy as a risk factor

The two most common types of empathy are emotional and cognitive. Cognitive empathy allows people to understand another person's pain by placing themselves in that person's shoes. The definition of affective empathy, according to Young, Fox, and Zahn-Waxler (1999), is "an emotional response characterised by feelings of concern for another and a desire to alleviate that person's distress." Emotional empathy is the ability to feel another person's emotions, whereas cognitive empathy is the ability to understand another person's sentiments. Jolliffe & Farrington (2007) state that they are not incompatible with one another and that they can both coexist. It is believed that reduced affective empathy is one of the primary characteristics of psychopathy. This disorder is prevalent in psychopaths who exhibit a range of psychological and behavioural characteristics that tend antisocial and deviant behaviours. According to behavioural tendencies analysis, psychopaths seem to be able to understand other people's emotions but not be able to feel them themselves. Stated differently, their empathy tendencies are cognitive rather than affective (Jolliffe & Farrington, 2007).

Cognitive and Language Deficiencies as Risk Factors

Contrary to popular belief, most boys have linguistic and cognitive deficits that result in antisocial behaviour (Snow & Powell, 2012). Language impediment refers to issues

in understanding others or expressing oneself and adolescents who had such deficits as youngsters—usually between the ages of five and ten—were found to have a higher likelihood of participating in delinquent conduct as adolescents as compared to children who did not have such impairments.

The onset of delinquent behaviour is influenced by rejections and unfavourable responses from a range of social groups, including peer groups and educators, according to a thorough analysis of the causal relationship between this effect and delinquent behaviour (Véronneau & Dishion, 2011). Due to their poor and lacking academic performance, which undermines their stability and confidence, children with language issues frequently display early warning indications of deviation. Their frequent frustrations escalate into violent and disruptive behaviour that starts at home and spreads to all areas of social contact when left unchecked.

2.8 Social Deviance

Any activity that detrimentally impacts other people physically or psychologically, or their property, is considered socially deviant (Baba, *et al.*, 2019). Among other things, socially aberrant behaviour includes stealing, lying, sexual immorality, and harming others. Clare (2006) defines socially deviant behaviour as harmful actions that exhibit apparent and intentional hostility towards other people. It includes all types of disorderliness or behavioural disorders that reinforce societal evils in the community.

2.9.1 School and Social Behaviour

The socio-temporal environment of the classroom has an impact on student behaviour. A child's educational environment can have an impact on their social behaviours. Students' poor performance on external exams was caused, in part, by indiscipline, a lack of infrastructure, and administrative misbehaviour by principals, claim Mbaabu

and Orodho (2014). Cheng (2012) made a connection between students' abnormal behaviour and their family's socioeconomic standing as well as their interactions with their instructors. Teachers often use passive learning strategies in classes with a large number of pupils, which might result in disruptive behaviours (Yaman & Uygumada, 2009).

Edinyang (2017) lists several well-known aspects of the school environment that can significantly contribute to socially deviant behaviour from affected students, including crowded classrooms, harsh punishments, student isolation, ineffective supervision, a lack of social infrastructure, a lack of academic support for students, a lack of student involvement and choice in the learning process, a sense of rejection from peers, a lack of concern from friends, teachers, and the principal, the controversial use of corporal punishment, and a lack of academic support for students with behavioural issues and academic challenges. According to Belle (2017), teachers who fail to instil in their pupils the qualities of great and admirable behaviour will affect the behaviours that their students deem proper and wrong.

A school with inadequate management, supervision, discipline, and dedication to its duties, according to Kwamta *et al.* (2021), creates a society where there is a lack of intervention, which in turn influences drug use, gang violence, and absenteeism. Strict regulations and limitations in schools can frustrate and disappoint students, which may lead to disruptive behaviour (Amie-Ogan, *et al.*, 2022).

2.9.2 Peer Pressure and Social Behaviour

Due to the influence of their playmates, students are far more inclined to engage in inappropriate activities that could endanger themselves or others (Belle, 2017). Peer pressure can lead students to use drugs, alcohol, tobacco, and weapons to make threats

and harass other students who do not belong to their group or who do not share their opinions. They may also take part in other illegal gang operations (Belle, 2017). To express their disagreement disapproval of and opposition to the administration, they violate rules and regulations. Their primary behaviour is hence antisocial (Johnson, *et al.*, 2012).

2.9.3 Society and socially deviant behaviour

An important factor influencing a student's exposure to present-day deviant activities is whether or not they live in a neighbourhood with social disorders (Belle, 2017). In dysfunctional communities, there is high unemployment, limited educational opportunities, poverty, violence, and drug use. Because of the dysfunctional community that was created when the original goal was not accomplished, students may engage in an array of various kinds of social deviance (Gambo & Muktar, 2017). Students' deviant social behaviour in the classroom reflects chaotic signs in the community that surround society as an entirety (Belle, 2017). Denga (2002) also notes that society actively contributes to a child's socialisation.

The goal of society's agents, including the government, parents, teachers, chiefs, and others, is to assist teenagers in reining in the tendency to act out. It is challenging to stop deviant behaviour in environments where law enforcement is incompetent, unfair, biased, and corrupt (Akinsanya, 2024).

2.9.4 The family and socially deviant behaviour

Teenagers' conduct and socialisation are greatly influenced by their families. Parental hostility, drug and weapon use, having access to and using dangerous weapons at home, and parent divorce or separation are some family characteristics that might negatively impact children's behaviour (Belle, 2017).

Teenagers who experience interpersonal conflict are more prone to act immorally in the classroom, according to Cluver, Bowes, and Gardner (2010). Students may acquire particular disaffections with others based on restrictive-permissive parental conduct, dependence-independence, and cooperation-competition (Kumari & Kumar, 2017). This affects the student's opinions and social abilities. Furthermore, the socioeconomic position of the family could influence the behaviour of the student.

Teenage academic achievement and conduct are associated, according to Khaliq *et al.* (2016), with parental money, status, and occupation in a relatively positive way. Arum & Ford (2012) claim that the greater the social and economic divide the greater the likelihood of disruptive behaviour among youths in schools. According to Saleem (2020), family dissolutions including divorce, separation, and marital strife rob kids of stability, social chances, and parental love, all of which have detrimental psychological effects on the kids.

2.9.5 The new media and socially deviant behaviour

Due to their constant “multitasking”, teenagers’ lives are now dominated by new media. They commonly use their phone to simultaneously publish messages (chat) on social networks while attending their classes (Belle, 2017). According to O’Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson (2011), children who use social media excessively also run the risk of participating in dangerous activities like bullying, Facebook depression, clique forming, sexting, betting, and other self-destructive behaviours. Moreover, there are claims that teens who play video games and too much screen time behave aggressively toward colleagues and other authorities (Holfert, 2010; Denwigwe, *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, in this era of swift technological advancement, new media has a detrimental impact on pupils’ behaviours (Beebeejaun-Muslum), 2014).

2.9 Theoretical Framework

Do criminals develop through circumstances or are they born that way? (The Debate: Nature versus Nurture). Although a person may not be born with criminal traits, they may eventually acquire them through time.

2.10.1 The Theory of Differential Association

The Differential Association theory, first put forth by Edwin H. Sutherland in 1939, maintains that social interaction is how people acquire values and get motivated to commit crimes (Bosiakoh, 2012). The idea's fundamental tenet is that humans are neutral beings from birth. Humans acquire knowledge through social interaction, observation of the behaviour of individuals around them, and participation in small, intimate groups. They gain the skills required to perpetrate these crimes, but they also learn the ability to rationalise and justify them since they anticipate or receive a greater benefit than the consequence of their acts. (Clinard *et al.*, 2014). Differential connections can vary in priority, strength, duration, and frequency. One eventually picks up deviant behaviour as one come into contact with both non-deviant and deviant patterns.

The method by which aberrant behaviour is acquired is not especially exceptional. A person's unsettling character can be formed by a variety of sociological factors, such as poverty, parent loss, a challenging upbringing, society, etc. Adolescents who socialise with their peers who engage in or endorse these practices regularly are more likely to display deviant behaviour.

2.10.2 The Strain Theory

The strain theory was created by Robert K. Merton and maintains that people are usually pressured by society to live up to socially acceptable norms without being

provided with the means to do so. Strain theorists contend that a family's financial constraints may directly contribute to delinquency since impoverished kids may not have the means to pursue their desired social and economic objectives. People who are under stress lose their natural inclination to defy social conventions in order to satisfy their demands. The imbalance between a goal and the means required to achieve it results in anger and deviant behaviour.

Teenagers may become tense if they are unable to employ legal means to achieve socially accepted goals (such as becoming wealthy or excelling academically). People who are frustrated by the disparity could turn to abnormal activity as a solution to achieve these goals. Marwah & Deflem (2006) claim that the strain theory is unable to explain violent crimes or minor transgressions that incite public dread. Differential association theory and strain theory are similar in many aspects since they both centre on the occurrence of "strains" in society. Nonetheless, there is a crucial distinction between the two presumptions since the former maintains that individuals are "neutral" from birth and the latter maintains that individuals are "conforming." One major difference between the two theories is that in the case of Differential Association Theory, strains to fulfil desires cause people to deviate from their neutral nature towards deviance, whereas in the case of Strain Theory, people deviate from their naturally conforming nature to meet their needs.

2.10.3 The General Theory of Crime

The General Theory of Crime by Gottfredson & Hirschi (1990), which Burt referenced in his 2020 study, states that deficiencies in self-control are the primary cause of crime and delinquency. A strong social connect between a parent and kid can prevent delinquent behaviour, according to control theory. However, a low SES could

leave parents stressed out, which can lead to less harmonious parent-child relationships. The value of social connections is one thing that deters criminal activity. It is commonly believed that unstable or damaged social interactions lead to delinquency. Wambua (2015) highlighted Welch's previous research, which suggests that adolescents and teenagers who have strong social links, behave in a socially acceptable way, and uphold societal norms and values are less likely to participate in antisocial activity. Furthermore, rather than emphasising individual personalities, the idea highlighted the significance of family coherence and integration. Thus, the theory identifies peer interactions in addition to familial dynamics as a major factor in delinquent behaviour (Burfeind & Bartusch, 2015). Socialisation serves to curb these intrinsic tendencies that may lead to unlawful or aberrant behaviour. According to Wambua (2015), it emphasises restraint as a protection against criminality (Welch, 1998). Strong social links to one's family, school, and community are essential for deterring abnormal behaviour, in Hirschi's opinion.

According to a recent study, self-control may be dynamic and subject to change over time, contrary to Gottfredson and Hirschi's contention in their General Theory of Crime that self-control is a lifelong quality that starts in early childhood (Burt, Simons & Simons, 2006; Hay & Forrest 2010). Feeling involved and connected reduces the likelihood of aberrant behaviour in adolescents.

2.11 Conceptual framework

The home factors: these refer to the influences and conditions within the individual families, they include the parenting practices adopted by the parents, family structure, parent-child relationship, socioeconomic characteristics, family values and norms, substance abuse and criminality within the family. They may contribute to teenage

deviant behaviours by modelling antisocial behaviours, failing to provide adequate supervision and guidance, creating stress or instability, influencing their attitudes and values or limiting opportunities. Generally, home factors are factors within the control of the family.

Societal factors, shaped by broader social structure are influences and conditions within an individual's social environment and is out of the control of the individual. These factors include peer pressure, school environment, social media, socioeconomic inequality, community disorganization, social isolation, systemic injustice and lack of community resources. They contribute to teenage crimes and deviant behaviours through social learning (observing and imitating others), social pressure (pressurizing an individual to engage in acts to fit in, gain acceptance or avoid rejection), exposing teenagers to a culture that condones or promotes antisocial behaviours in a neighbourhood rife with crimes, poverty, unemployment, social injustice, systemic inequality and inadequate supervision.

The variables that determine the association between the home factors, societal factors and criminal and deviant behaviour of teenagers are displayed in the conceptual framework (Figure 1). The socioeconomic characteristics, parenting style, school environment, peer pressure, social media and its association to behaviours. There are three categories of variable: independent, dependent and intervening variables. Respondent's school environment, peer pressure and social media usage and their parents' parenting style and socioeconomic status are the independent variables. Dependent variables are criminal behaviour and deviant behaviour. Low self-esteem, social skills, mental health, personality type, attachment style, genetics, culture and temperament are examples of intervening variables.

2.11.1 Explanation of the conceptual framework

This seeks to explain the interconnectedness between societal factors (social media, peer pressure, school environment), home factors (parenting style, socio-personal characteristics), criminal behaviours and deviant behaviours among teenagers with the intervention of the listed variables. It suggests that independent variables interact with the intervening variables to increase the likelihood of criminal and deviant behaviours. The home and societal factors interact with the intervening variables either by

Enhancement, which strengthens the effects of the intervening variables on behaviours

Increasing risks and shaping behaviours: variables like low self-esteem, poor social skills or mental health issues would increase the propensity to turn to antisocial behaviours while culture, personality, and attachment style shape the type or severity of criminal and deviant behaviours.

Buffer or moderator: socio-personal characteristics, parenting styles, school environment, peer pressure and social media buffer and moderate intervening variables. The buffering of listed intervening variables by independent variables weakens the effect on criminal and deviant behaviours, intervening variables are moderated by changing the direction or strength of the relationship by independent variables to change the resulting behaviours.

2.11.2 Possible pathways to criminal and deviant behaviours

Social media usage and exposure could lead to low self-esteem.

Peer pressure could influence genetics, temperament and personality of the individual.

Parenting style could affect attachment style, social skills and mental health.

School environment could influence culture, social skills and mental health.

Socio-personal characteristics could lead to low self-esteem and poor social skills.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the study design, study area, population, sampling techniques, instrument for the data collection and method of data analysis.

3.1 Study Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to assess Factors contributing to Crimes or Deviant Behaviour among Teenagers in Public Secondary Schools in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

3.2 The study area

The study was conducted in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria.

3.2.1 Description of Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State

Lagos State has the highest population of youth in Nigeria accounting for over 6.1% of the total youth population of the country (NBS, 2012). Alimosho Local Government Area (6°36'38"N 3°17'45"E), the most populous Local Government Area in Nigeria with a population of 2,249,896 people according to the Lagos Bureau of Statistics (2009) was established in 1945 under the Western region. It shares border with Agege, Ifako – Ijaye, Ikeja, Oshodi – Isolo, Amuwo Odofin and Ojo Local Government Areas. Alimosho is the Local Government Area that has a high number of public secondary schools (52 - 30 junior secondary and 22 senior secondary schools) in Lagos State with a total population of 77,465 students as of 2019 (Annual School Census Report LASG Ministry of Education, 2019). Due to the large youth population of Alimosho LGA, its crime rate is high with cult clash, robbery, thuggery and so many other crimes constantly being reported in the news.

Figure 2: Map of Lagos showing Alimosho Local Government Area

Alimosho has now been subdivided into Local Council Development Areas (LCDA).

The six sub-divisions created out of the old Alimosho are:

Agbado/Oke-odo LCDA,

Ayobo/Ipaja LCDA,

Alimosho LCDA contains the urban area of Egbeda/Akowonjo.

Egbe/Idimu LCDA,

Ikotun/Igando LCDA and

Mosan/Okunola LCDA.

3.2.2 Study Location

The study was conducted in four (4) schools in four (4) selected LCDAs.

3.3 Population of the Study

The targeted population of this study were teenagers with criminal or deviant behaviours, between age 13 – 19 years in selected secondary schools in selected Local Community Development Areas of Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State.

3.3.1 Inclusion criteria

- Every willing teenager in the selected schools in the study area was used for the research survey.
- Informed consent was given by the respondents.

3.3.2 Exclusion criteria

- Youths who did not give consent to participating in the research survey.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted. The stages include the following:

Stage 1: A random sampling technique was used to select four (4) Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) from the Six (6) LCDAs in Alimosho Local Government Area.

Stage 2: A random sampling method by ball rolling was used to select the following schools in the selected Four (4) Local Council Development Areas.

- 1) Abesan High School in Mosan/Okunola LCDA
- 2) Ijegun Comprehensive High School in Ikotun/Igando LCDA
- 3) Oke-Odo Senior High School in Agbado/Oke-Odo LCDA
- 4) Community High School in Egbe/Idimu LCDA

Stage 3: The purposive sampling method was used to select 269 students with deviant or criminal behaviour across JS 3 – SS 3 students from each selected school for the study.

3.5 Sample size

According to Taro Yamane (1967) with the formula as cited by Otabor & Obahiaghon (2016).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= sample size,

N= population size

e = the acceptable sampling error of 0.05

1 = number of items in the population

$$n = \frac{667}{1 + 667(0.05)^2} = \frac{667}{1 + 667(0.0025)}$$

$$= \frac{667}{1+1.6675} = \frac{667}{2.6675} = 250.04 \approx 250.$$

However, 10% of the calculated sample size was added because of the non-response rate.

$$\frac{250*10}{100} = \frac{2500}{100} = 25.$$

$$= 250 + 25 = 275$$

However, 269 questionnaires were retrieved and used for this study.

3.6 Sample Fraction

Sample fraction was used to calculate the number of teenagers with known deviant or criminal behaviours selected in each public secondary school.

$$\text{Sampling fraction} = \frac{\text{sample size}}{\text{Total population}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sampling fraction} &= \frac{250}{667} \\ &= 0.375 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the sampling fraction is multiplied by the number of teenagers

$$0.375 \times A = B$$

Where, A = number of teenagers in each school

B = number of teenagers selected for sampling.

Table 2: Sampling frame of the study

Selected High Schools	No. of students with known deviant behaviour	No. of selected students using sample fraction (0.375)
Abesan Junior High School (JS3)	26	10
Abesan Senior High School (SS1)	29	11
Abesan Senior High School (SS2)	37	14
Abesan Senior High School (SS3)	33	12
Ijegun Junior Comprehensive High School (JS3)	38	14
Ijegun Senior Comprehensive High School (SS1)	47	18
Ijegun Senior Comprehensive High School(SS2)	49	18
Ijegun Senior Comprehensive High School (SS3)	52	20
Community Junior Secondary School (JS3)	37	14
Community Senior Secondary School (SS1)	45	17
Community Senior Secondary School (SS2)	46	16
Community Senior Secondary School (SS3)	45	17
Oke-Odo Junior High School (JS3)	56	21
Oke-Odo Senior High School (SS1)	48	18
Oke-Odo Senior High School (SS2)	45	17
Oke-Odo Senior High School (SS3)	34	13
Total	667	250

Source: Field survey 2024

3.7 Instrument for data collection

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire on “Factors contributing to Crimes and Deviant Behaviour of Teenagers in Public Secondary Schools in Alimosho Local Government Lagos State Nigeria” (FCCDBTQ). The questionnaire contained 7 sections as follows:

Section A: Demographic information

Section B: Socio-economic information.

Section C: Deviant behaviours engaged in by respondents.

Section D: Criminal behaviour of respondents.

Section E: Parenting styles experienced by the respondents.

Section F: School environment of the respondents.

.Section G: Peer pressure effect on the respondents.

Section H: Social media usage of the respondents.

3.8 Validation and reliability of instrument for data collection

3.8.1 Validation of instrument for data collection

The questionnaire on “Factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviour of teenagers in Public Secondary Schools in Alimosho Local Government Lagos State Nigeria” (FCCDBTQ) was subjected to face and content validation by the researcher’s supervisors.

They were asked to review the instrument's items for word clarity, appropriateness, perceptions, and work-related relevance. Every one of their suggestions was followed to the letter.

3.8.2 Reliability of instrument for data collection

A trial test procedure was used to test the reliability of the instrument for consistency by administering 25 questionnaires to students of Ijaiye-Ojokoro Senior School Ijaiye which is outside the study area.

Table 3: Result of Reliability of Instrument.

S/N	Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Number of items	Status
1	Criminal behaviour	0.821	15	Reliable
2	Deviant behaviour	0.887	11	Reliable
3	Parenting style	0.894	16	Reliable
4	School environment	0.785	16	Reliable
5	Peer pressure	0.861	19	Reliable
6	Social media use	0.914	28	Reliable

Source: Preliminary Field Survey, 2024.

3.9 Method of data collection

a. Demographic characteristics

- i. The sex of respondents was measured at a nominal level as male (1), female (0)
- ii. Age: this was measured at an ordinal level as 13-15 (1), 16-18 (2), Above 19 years (3)
- iii. Class of respondent: this was measured at an ordinal level as JSS3 (0), SS1 (1), SS2 (2) and SS3 (3).
- iv. Religion was measured at a nominal level as Christianity (1), Islam (2), Traditional (3) and No religion (4).
- v. Type of home: this was measured at a nominal level as monogamous (0), polygamous (1), Single parent (2)

b. Socioeconomic information

- i. Household size was measured at interval level
- ii. The level of Education was measured at ordinal intervals. No Formal Education (1), Primary Education (2), Secondary Education (3), Tertiary Education (4).
- iii. Occupation: this was measured at nominal level
- iv. Yearly income was measured at an interval level by asking how much the respondents' parent earn every year.

c. Deviant Behaviours

The deviant behaviour of respondents was measured by an adapted version of the “Deviant Behaviour Variety scale: Development and validation with a sample of

Portuguese adolescents” by Sanches, *et al.*, (2016) and this was measured using the 5-point Likert scale.

d. Criminal Behaviours

The criminal behaviour of respondents was measured by an adapted version of the “Measures of Criminal Attitudes and Association: Development, Factor, Structure and Validity” scale by Mills, *et al.*, (2002). Criminal attitudes and associations were measured by a 5-point Likert scale after asking respondents about their criminal behaviour.

e. Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic Status of respondents was measured by an adapted version of the “Modified Kuppuswamy Socioeconomic Scale” by Saleem & Jan (2019).

f. Parenting Style

The parenting style adopted by respondents’ parent and how it contributes to crimes and deviant behaviour was measured by an adapted version of the “Construction and Validation of Scale of Parenting Style” by Abdul Gafor & Kurukkan (2014)

g. School Environment

The school environment of respondents and how it contributes to crimes and deviant behaviour was measured by an adapted version of the “Development of a School _ Level Environment Questionnaire” by Rentoul & Fisher (1983).

h. Peer Pressure

The effect of peer pressure on respondents and how it contributes to crimes and deviant behaviour was measured by an adapted version of the “Peer Pressure: Measuring Peer Pressure, Popularity and Conformity in Adolescent Boys and Girls:

Predicting School Performance, sexual Attitudes and Substance Abuse” by Santor, *et al.*, (2000).

i. Social Media Usage

Social media use of respondents and how it contributes to crimes and deviant behaviour was measured by adapting the “Social Networking Usage Questionnaire” by Gupta & Bashir (2018).

3.10 Method of data analysis

The data collected were subjected to Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.0. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, standard deviation and percentages were used to analyse the objectives while inferential statistics: Chi-square, Pearson Moment Correlation (PPMC), Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method and student t test were used to analyse the research hypotheses.

3.11 Ethical consideration

Approval to conduct this study was obtained from the Workforce, Planning and Recruitment unit of Education District (1) of the Lagos State Ministry of Education and approval was also obtained from the Department of Home Science and Management (FUNAAB). The study respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and were also informed that they could refuse to take part or voluntarily withdraw from the survey at any time.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected on factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviours among teenagers in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government, Lagos State, Nigeria, is presented in this chapter. Two hundred sixty-nine (n = 269) Alimosho secondary school students provided the data. The findings are displayed in subsections.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4 displays the demographic characteristics of the respondents, with 52.0 per cent being female and 48.0% being male. Also 52.0% of the respondents were between the ages of 16 – 18 years, 24.2% was between the ages of 13 – 15 years, and 23.8% were older than 18 years. Additional results from Table 3 indicates that 35.7% of the respondents were in SSS3, 28.7% in SSS2, 20.1% in SSS1, and 15.6% in JSS3. Furthermore 1.9% of respondents practiced African Tradition Religion, 36.4% were Muslims, and the majority of respondents (61.7%) were Christians. Results also reveal that 36.1% of the respondents came from polygamous homes, while the bulk of respondents (63.9%) were from monogamous families.

Table 4: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (n = 269)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	129	48.0
Female	140	52.0
Age		
13 - 15	65	24.2
16 - 18	140	52.0
Above 18	64	23.8
Class		
JSS3	42	15.6
SSS1	54	20.1
SSS2	77	28.6
SSS3	96	35.7
Religion		
Christianity	166	61.7
Islam	98	36.4
Traditional	5	1.9
Type of home		
Polygamous	97	36.1
Monogamous	172	63.9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2 Socioeconomic Characteristics of respondents' parents

The socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents' parents are presented in Table 5. 66% of the respondents had four to seven members in their families, 22% had seven to nine members, 8% had fewer than four members, and 4% had more than nine members. Twenty-four percent of the respondents' parents made less than ₦500,000 while eleven percent made more than ₦5,000,000. Majority of respondents' parents (39.8%) made between ₦500,000 - ₦2,000,000 annually, followed by 27.9% who made between ₦2,000,000 - ₦5,000,000.

When it comes to education, the results indicates that 44.2% of fathers possessed HND/BSc certificate, 23.8% had a Postgraduate certificate, 16.0% had ND/NCE, 4.1% had SSCE, 4.1% had a primary certificate, and 7.8% had never attended any formal schooling. In contrast, 36.4% of mothers had HND/BSc certificate, 27.9% had ND/NCE, 19.7% had SSCE, and 16.0% had Postgraduate certificates, while none of them have ever had a primary education. Table 4 further reveals that the fathers' occupations were as follows: 31.6% worked for themselves, 24.2% were traders or business owners, 20.4% were artisans, 15.6% were civil servants, and 8.2% were unemployed. However, the majority of mothers' jobs (36.1%) were as traders or business owners, followed by civil servants (24.6%), private employees (16.4%), artisans (15.6%), and those without employment (7.8%).

Table 5: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents' Parents (n = 269)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Household size		
≤ 3	22	8.2
4 - 6	163	60.6
7 - 9	73	27.1
Above 9	11	4.1
Annual Income		
< ₦500,000	55	20.4
₦500,000 - ₦2,000,000	107	39.8
₦2,000,000 - ₦5,000,000	75	27.9
Above ₦5,000,000	32	11.9
Father's Level of Education		
No formal education	21	7.8
Primary	11	4.1
SSCE	11	4.1
ND / NCE	43	16.0
University / HND	119	44.2
Postgraduate	64	23.8
Mother's Level of Education		
No formal education	0	0.0
Primary	0	0.0
Secondary	53	19.7
ND / NCE	75	27.9
University / HND	98	36.4
Postgraduate	43	16.0
Father's Occupation		
Civil servant	42	15.6
Artisan	55	20.4
Unemployed	65	24.2
Trader/Business	85	31.6
Private employee	22	8.2
Mother's Occupation		
Civil servant	65	24.2
Artisan	42	15.6
Unemployed	97	36.1
Trader/Business	44	16.4
Private employee	21	7.8

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.3 Criminal behaviours

Table 6 displays the outcomes of the criminal activity that the respondents exhibited. The findings show that the respondents indicated they were friends with criminals who were well-known to the police ($\bar{x} = 3.67$), they knew multiple persons who had committed crimes ($\bar{x} = 3.64$), and they were accepted by their criminal associates ($\bar{x} = 3.39$). Some of the respondents indicated that none of their acquaintances had ever desired to commit a crime ($\bar{x} = 3.06$) and ($\bar{x} = 2.95$) of respondents admitted they lacked respect for authority.

Criminal behaviour was divided into three categories: high, moderate, and low to assess respondents' degree of deviance. Figure 3 shows that 35.7% and 28.3% of the respondents, respectively, exhibit high and low levels of criminal conduct, whereas 36.1% of the respondents display a moderate degree of criminal behaviour.

Table 6: Criminal behaviour engaged in by the respondents (n = 269)

SN	Questions	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	\bar{x}	Std.d.
1	Criminal friends who are well-known to the police	86(32)	97(36.1)	42(15.6)	-	44(16.4)	3.67	1.36
2	I know several people who have committed crimes	119(44.2)	53(19.7)	32(11.9)	11(4.1)	54(20.1)	3.64	1.55
3	I am accepted by my criminal friends.	64(23.8)	75(27.9)	75(27.9)	11(4.1)	44(16.4)	3.39	1.34
4	None of my friends has ever wanted to commit a crime.	76(28.3)	65(24.2)	11(4.1)	32(11.9)	85(31.6)	3.06	1.66
5	Lack of respect for authority.	32(11.9)	42(15.6)	119(44.2)	32(11.9)	44(16.4)	2.95	1.19
6	Sense of kinship with lawbreakers.	42(15.6)	43(16)	32(11.9)	119(44.2)	33(12.3)	2.78	1.30
7	Committed a crime before.	20(7.4)	97(36.1)	11(4.1)	65(24.2)	76(28.3)	2.70	1.40
8	Most of my friends don't have criminal records.	32(11.9)	21(7.8)	33(12.3)	128(47.6)	55(20.4)	2.43	1.24
9	None of my friends have committed crimes	-	75(27.9)	-	108(40.1)	86(32)	2.24	1.18
10	Stealing and holding it against anyone	-	85(31.6)	10(3.7)	55(20.4)	119(44.2)	2.23	1.30
11	Have criminal friends.	-	54(20.1)	53(19.7)	22(8.2)	140(52)	2.08	1.23
Grand mean							2.83	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

\bar{x} = Mean, Std.d. = Standard Deviation. Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

Figure 3: Level of Criminal Behaviour

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.4 Deviant Behaviour

Deviant behaviours exhibited by respondents are presented in Table 7. The findings showed that the respondents indicated they had lied to adults (family members, teachers, etc.) ($\bar{x} = 3.71$), committed petty theft ($\bar{x} = 3.38$), threatened or insulted people online ($\bar{x} = 3.20$), attended a cult meeting ($\bar{x} = 2.89$), carried a weapon (knife, pistol, etc.) ($\bar{x} = 2.84$), bet or engaged in sports betting ($\bar{x} = 2.83$), skipped class because they didn't feel like it ($\bar{x} = 2.68$), struck someone (students, siblings, teachers, families, security guard, etc.) ($\bar{x} = 2.64$), raped or been raped ($\bar{x} = 2.60$) and had multiple sex partners ($\bar{x} = 2.55$).

To assess the degree of deviant behaviour among respondents, three categories—high, moderate, and low—were used for deviant behaviours. Figure 4 shows that slightly more than half (52.0%) of the respondents displayed moderately deviant behaviour, whereas low and high deviant behaviour were displayed by 32% and 16.0% of the respondents, respectively.

Table 7: Deviant behaviours engaged in by the respondents (n = 269)

During the last year, have you ever....	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	\bar{x}	Std.d.
Do you Lie to adults (e.g., family members, teachers, etc.)?	95(35.3)	33(12.3)	119(44.2)	11(4.1)	11(4.1)	3.71	1.12
How often have you engaged in petty theft?	63(23.4)	86(32)	54(20.1)	22(8.2)	44(16.4)	3.38	1.36
Do you insult or threaten anyone online?	33(12.3)	97(36.1)	74(27.5)	22(8.2)	43(16)	3.20	1.24
How regularly do you attend a cult meeting?	44(16.4)	65(24.2)	53(19.7)	31(11.5)	76(28.3)	2.89	1.46
How often do you carry a weapon (e.g., knife, pistol, etc.)?	21(7.8)	76(28.3)	65(24.2)	52(19.3)	55(20.4)	2.84	1.26
How often do you engage in betting or sport betting?	75(27.9)	31(11.5)	22(8.2)	54(20.1)	87(32.3)	2.83	1.65
How often do you skip classes because you didn't feel like going, to stay with colleagues, or to go for a ride?	11(4.1)	96(35.7)	11(4.1)	97(36.1)	54(20.1)	2.68	1.26
How often do you hit anybody (e.g., students, siblings, teacher, family, security guard, etc.)?	22(8.2)	53(19.7)	43(16)	109(40.5)	42(15.6)	2.64	1.20
Do you rape or have been raped?	33(12.3)	96(35.7)	-	11(4.1)	129(48)	2.60	1.63
How often do you have sex with multiple sex partners?	11(4.1)	85(31.6)	43(16)	32(11.9)	98(36.4)	2.55	1.36
How often have you been involved in armed robbery?	44(16.4)	32(11.9)	32(11.9)	10(3.7)	151(56.1)	2.29	1.60
Do you drink alcohol?	-	42(15.6)	86(32)	43(16)	98(36.4)	2.27	1.11
How often do you vandalize any property?	42(15.6)	21(7.8)	-	86(32)	120(44.6)	2.18	1.46
When do you get involved in street or gang fight?	21(7.8)	11(4.1)	53(19.7)	85(31.6)	99(36.8)	2.14	1.19
Do you take substance abuse?	-	11(4.1)	95(35.3)	64(23.8)	99(36.8)	2.07	0.94
Grand mean						2.68	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

\bar{x} = Mean, Std.d. = Standard Deviation. Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

Figure 4: Level of Deviant Behaviour

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.5 Factors Contributing to Criminal and Deviant Behaviours among Respondents in the study area

Peer pressure, social media use, educational environments, and styles of parenting were the variables taken into account in this study. Results in Table 7-10 indicates that the primary characteristics associated with criminal and deviant behaviours among the respondents were the school environment ($\bar{x} = 3.71$) and parental styles ($\bar{x} = 2.95$). Respondents' criminal and deviant behaviours were also found to be significantly influenced by peer pressure ($\bar{x} = 2.71$) and social media use ($\bar{x} = 2.45$).

4.5.1 School environment

The results in Table 8 present the school environment as reported by respondents. Respondents indicated that there are too many students in a class ($\bar{x} = 4.41$), that not all students are treated fairly and equally ($\bar{x} = 4.16$), that they feel bullied or harassed by other students or teachers ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), that there is not enough technology or resources in the school to support students' learning ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), that they often feel that their teachers don't understand or care about their needs ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), that they are overburdened with schoolwork ($\bar{x} = 3.85$), that there is too much pressure to perform well academically ($\bar{x} = 3.84$), and that classes are held in dilapidated buildings ($\bar{x} = 3.80$) and the lack of extracurricular activities and programs offered at school for students to participate in ($\bar{x} = 3.80$) were all highly regarded as factors influencing misbehaving.

However, they rated feeling alone or excluded by their peers ($\bar{x} = 2.75$) and finding it difficult to establish friends and get along with other students at school ($\bar{x} = 2.68$) low.

Table 8: School environment experience of the respondents (n = 269)

Questions	SA	A	U	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.d.
There is an overpopulation of students in a class	130(48.3)	119(44.2)	20(7.4)	-	-	4.41	0.63
There aren't enough resources (e.g. counselling) available at school to help students with mental health issues	130(48.3)	96(35.7)	32(11.9)	11(4.1)	-	4.28	0.83
Not everyone at school is treated fairly and equally	53(19.7)	205(76.2)	11(4.1)	-	-	4.16	0.46
I have felt bullied or harassed by other students or teachers at school	64(23.8)	162(60.2)	32(11.9)	-	11(4.1)	4.00	0.85
The school lacks enough technology and resources to support my learning	-	269(100)	-	-	-	4.00	0.00
Sometimes, I feel like my teachers don't understand or care about my needs	42(15.6)	184(68.4)	32(11.9)	11(4.1)	-	3.96	0.66
I often feel stressed or overwhelmed by schoolwork	-	238(88.5)	21(7.8)	10(3.7)	-	3.85	0.45
There is too much pressure to do well academically at school	43(16)	139(51.7)	87(32.3)	-	-	3.84	0.68
Classes are received in dilapidated buildings	107(39.8)	97(36.1)	-	33(12.3)	32(11.9)	3.80	1.39
There aren't enough extracurricular activities and programs available for me to participate in at school	32(11.9)	162(60.2)	64(23.8)	11(4.1)	-	3.80	0.69
The school doesn't provide enough opportunities for me to grow and develop outside of academics	42(15.6)	86(32)	141(52.4)	-	-	3.63	0.74
I have felt bored or uninterested in what I'm learning at school	21(7.8)	131(48.7)	96(35.7)	21(7.8)	-	3.57	0.75
I have witnessed or experienced violence or threats at school	-	173(64.3)	53(19.7)	10(3.7)	33(12.3)	3.36	1.02
There aren't enough textbooks and materials for me to use at school	-	152(56.5)	75(27.9)	11(4.1)	31(11.5)	3.29	0.99
I have felt isolated or left out by my classmates	-	22(8.2)	159(59.1)	88(32.7)	-	2.75	0.59
I find it challenging to make friends and get along with other students at school	11(4.1)	64(23.8)	43(16)	129(48)	22(8.2)	2.68	1.05
Grand mean						3.71	0.74

Source: Field Survey, 2024

SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, U= Undecided, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree,

Std.d. = Standard Deviation.

Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

4.5.2 Parenting Styles

Four basic domains - authoritarian, negligent, overprotective, and permissive - were used to measure parenting styles.

Results in Table 9 highlights the prevalence of authoritative parenting ($\bar{x} = 3.52$). According to respondents, adhering to their parents' guidelines was essential regardless of personal disagreements ($\bar{x} = 4.09$). Respondents said that when they make a mistake, their parents are more likely to be strict and critical than to be compassionate and supportive ($\bar{x} = 3.99$) and respondents found it challenging to confide in their parents, citing fear about their reactions ($\bar{x} = 3.24$).

The prevalence of overprotective parenting ($\bar{x} = 3.25$) was also high because parents' reactions to their children's attempts to assert their independence were often one of fear or anger ($\bar{x} = 3.55$), which discouraged children from expressing themselves. Additionally, parents who are overly controlling deny their children the freedom to make their own decisions or learn from their mistakes ($\bar{x} = 3.43$) and make them feel suffocated by their constant supervision and meddling in their lives ($\bar{x} = 3.43$). The grand mean of neglectful parenting was 2.78, reflecting the uneasiness and feelings of abandonment that respondents experience as a result of their parent's lack of involvement in their lives ($\bar{x} = 3.19$).

Respondents feel their parents are uninvolved towards them ($\bar{x} = 2.82$) and often too busy to attend to their needs ($\bar{x} = 2.74$), resulting in feelings of abandonment.

The grand mean for permissive parenting was 2.27. Respondents noted that they often felt that their parents are too lax and don't take their responsibilities seriously ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), that their parents prioritise being their friends over being their parents, which

can be confusing and leave them feeling unsupported ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), and that occasionally they wish their parents would give them more structure and guidance in their lives rather than letting them figure things out on their own ($\bar{x} = 2.20$).

Table 9: Parenting style adopted by respondents' parent (n = 269)

ITEMS	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	\bar{x}	Std.d.
Authoritarian Parenting						3.52	0.95
I feel like I have to obey my parents' rules all the time, even if I don't agree with them	119(44.2)	108(40.1)	-	32(11.9)	10(3.7)	4.09	1.12
When I make a mistake, my parents tend to be harsh and critical rather than understanding and supportive	63(23.4)	151(56.1)	44(16.4)	11(4.1)	-	3.99	0.75
I find it difficult to talk to my parents about my problems because I'm afraid of their reactions	11(4.1)	43(16)	215(79.9)	-	-	3.24	0.52
My parents often punish me without explaining why, making me feel frustrated and confused	64(23.8)	-	64(23.8)	87(32.3)	54(20.1)	2.75	1.42
Overprotective Parenting						3.25	1.19
When I try to assert my independence, my parents react with fear or anger, which makes me hesitant to express myself	64(23.8)	75(27.9)	97(36.1)	11(4.1)	22(8.2)	3.55	1.14
My parents are overly controlling and don't give me the freedom to make my own choices or learn from my mistakes	43(16)	108(40.1)	74(27.5)	11(4.1)	33(12.3)	3.43	1.18
I feel suffocated by my parents' constant monitoring and interference in my life, making it hard for me to develop independence	54(20.1)	74(27.5)	98(36.4)	21(7.8)	22(8.2)	3.43	1.14
I worry that my parents' overprotectiveness is hindering my ability to develop important life skills and cope with challenges on my own	22(8.2)	43(16)	85(31.6)	42(15.6)	77(28.6)	2.59	1.28
Neglectful Parenting						2.78	1.40
I struggle with feelings of abandonment and insecurity because of my parent's lack of involvement in my life	75(27.9)	64(23.8)	21(7.8)	55(20.4)	54(20.1)	3.19	1.53
I don't feel like my parents are interested in what's going on in my life or how I'm feeling	21(7.8)	106(39.4)	11(4.1)	66(24.5)	65(24.2)	2.82	1.38
My parents are often absent or preoccupied with their own lives, leaving me feeling neglected and alone	52(19.3)	21(7.8)	87(32.3)	22(8.2)	87(32.3)	2.74	1.47
I sometimes have to fend for myself because my parents aren't around to provide the support and guidance I need	10(3.7)	53(19.7)	54(20.1)	64(23.8)	88(32.7)	2.38	1.23
Permissive Parenting						2.27	1.43
I feel like my parents prioritize being my friend over being my parent, which can be confusing and leave me feeling unsupported	52(19.3)	43(16)	-	54(20.1)	120(44.6)	2.45	1.62
I often feel like my parents are too lenient and don't take my responsibilities seriously enough	64(23.8)	21(7.8)	31(11.5)	10(3.7)	143(53.2)	2.45	1.71
Sometimes, I wish my parents would provide more guidance and structure in my life instead of letting me figure things out on my own	43(16)	-	54(20.1)	42(15.6)	130(48.3)	2.20	1.45
My parents rarely set boundaries or enforce consequences for my actions, leading me to feel unsure of where the limits are	-	22(8.2)	43(16)	108(40.1)	96(35.7)	1.97	0.92
Grand mean						2.95	1.24

Source: Field Survey, 2024

\bar{x} = Mean, Std.d. = Standard Deviation. Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

4.5.3 Peer Pressure

The results in Table 10 present the type of influence peers have had on the respondents. The findings show that the respondents indicated they have lied to parents or authorities about their location or behaviour to avoid getting into trouble ($\bar{x} = 3.16$); they have taken risks or engaged in dangerous behaviour because their friends have done so ($\bar{x} = 2.95$); they have skipped class more frequently when their friends are absent ($\bar{x} = 2.91$); they have occasionally reacted against or disrespected their parents when they are upset or angry ($\bar{x} = 2.87$); they have felt pressured by their friends to engage in activities they don't want to ($\bar{x} = 2.87$); sometimes feel that they must smoke or drink to be accepted by their friends ($\bar{x} = 2.80$).

In addition, their friends frequently persuade them to agree with their ideas even when it is uncomfortable for them ($\bar{x} = 2.80$); they have also pretended to like things to fit in with their friends ($\bar{x} = 2.80$); and occasionally they feel as though they don't have to follow the rules established by authorities because they don't understand their point of view ($\bar{x} = 2.79$); they have skipped class because their friends were skipping ($\bar{x} = 2.79$); they have seen or heard about incidents of rape or sexual assault in their social circle ($\bar{x} = 2.75$); when their friends are around, they are more likely to try things they wouldn't normally do ($\bar{x} = 2.69$); and their friends have made them feel like they are not cool if they don't do what they do ($\bar{x} = 2.59$). Rape ($\bar{x} = 2.08$) and participation in cult activities ($\bar{x} = 2.24$) were rated low, though.

Table 10: Peer influence experience of the respondents (n = 269)

Statements	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	\bar{x}	Std.d.
I've lied to my parents or authorities on where I am or what I'm doing to avoid getting in trouble.	43(16)	75(27.9)	43(16)	97(36.1)	11(4.1)	3.16	1.19
My friends' use of drugs or alcohol makes me more likely to use them too.	75(27.9)	21(7.8)	65(24.2)	65(24.2)	43(16)	3.07	1.44
I've taken risks or done dangerous things because my friends dared me to.	85(31.6)	22(8.2)	54(20.1)	11(4.1)	97(36.1)	2.95	1.68
I skip class more often when my friends aren't attending.	31(11.5)	76(28.3)	21(7.8)	119(44.2)	22(8.2)	2.91	1.23
I sometimes talk back or disrespect my parents when I'm angry or upset.	85(31.6)	22(8.2)	-	97(36.1)	65(24.2)	2.87	1.63
I have felt pressured by my friends to do things I didn't want to do	42(15.6)	65(24.2)	32(11.9)	76(28.3)	54(20.1)	2.87	1.39
Sometimes I feel like I have to drink or smoke to be accepted by my friends.	22(8.2)	107(39.8)	22(8.2)	32(11.9)	86(32)	2.80	1.45
My friends often convince me to go along with their ideas even if I'm not comfortable.	42(15.6)	33(12.3)	65(24.2)	86(32)	43(16)	2.80	1.29
I've pretended to like something just to fit in with my friends.	11(4.1)	96(35.7)	54(20.1)	43(16)	65(24.2)	2.80	1.27
I sometimes feel like I don't need to follow the rules set by authorities because they don't understand my perspective.	85(31.6)	33(12.3)	11(4.1)	21(7.8)	119(44.2)	2.79	1.79
I have skipped class because my friends were skipping	11(4.1)	85(31.6)	32(11.9)	119(44.2)	22(8.2)	2.79	1.10
I have witnessed or heard about instances of sexual assault or rape in my social circle.	75(27.9)	11(4.1)	53(19.7)	33(12.3)	97(36.1)	2.75	1.63
When my friends are around, I'm more likely to try things I wouldn't normally try.	22(8.2)	44(16.4)	106(39.4)	22(8.2)	75(27.9)	2.69	1.26
I've found myself doing things I disagree with because my friends thought it was cool.	32(11.9)	75(27.9)	11(4.1)	75(27.9)	76(28.3)	2.67	1.44
My friends have made me feel like I'm not cool if I don't do what they do.	11(4.1)	96(35.7)	43(16)	11(4.1)	108(40.1)	2.59	1.42
I have been involved in sexual activities because I thought it would make me more popular.	22(8.2)	75(27.9)	21(7.8)	22(8.2)	129(48)	2.40	1.50
I've avoided doing things I enjoy because my friends wouldn't approve.	42(15.6)	33(12.3)	21(7.8)	54(20.1)	119(44.2)	2.35	1.52
I've been involved in cult activities	22(8.2)	43(16)	42(15.6)	32(11.9)	130(48.3)	2.24	1.40
I and my friends have been involved in raping	11(4.1)	22(8.2)	85(31.6)	11(4.1)	140(52)	2.08	1.24
Grand mean						2.71	1.41

Source: Field Survey, 2024

 \bar{x} = Mean, Std.d. = Standard Deviation. Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

4.5.4 Social Media Usage

The results of social networking tools used by respondents are presented in Table 11. The results show that respondents indicated spending too much time on social media or gaming, which causes them to neglect their relationships or responsibilities ($\bar{x} = 3.80$); and share sexually explicit messages, photos, or videos with peers—often without their consent ($\bar{x} = 3.59$); try to upset others by posting offensive or mean comments online ($\bar{x} = 3.23$); use the internet to cheat on exams ($\bar{x} = 3.19$); participate in unlawful or inappropriate online gambling ($\bar{x} = 2.94$); leak exam questions ($\bar{x} = 2.94$); share or view inappropriate pictures or videos online ($\bar{x} = 2.80$); and persistently bother or follow someone on the internet ($\bar{x} = 2.74$) and deceive others by disseminating false information or lies ($\bar{x} = 2.51$). The following actions were deemed low: hacking into computers or networks to steal data or cause harm ($\bar{x} = 1.27$), and using someone else's identity to steal money or steal information ($\bar{x} = 1.39$).

The findings on the social media platforms that the respondents utilised are shown in Figure 5. It can be seen from the results that the respondents' primary social network tools were Facebook ($\bar{x} = 4.24$), Instagram ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), TikTok ($\bar{x} = 4.08$), YouTube ($\bar{x} = 3.76$), and Twitter ($\bar{x} = 3.61$). However, Discord ($\bar{x} = 1.16$) and Tumblr ($\bar{x} = 1.40$) were ranked low.

Table 11: Social Media Usage of the Respondents (n = 269)

Items	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	\bar{x}	Std.d.
Excessive Screen Time: Spending too much time on social media or gaming, leads to neglect of responsibilities or relationships.	130(48.3)	20(7.4)	87(32.3)	-	32(11.9)	3.80	1.36
Sexting: Sharing sexually explicit messages, photos, or videos with peers, often without consent.	96(35.7)	54(20.1)	75(27.9)	-	44(16.4)	3.59	1.40
Trolling: Trying to make others upset by posting mean or offensive comments	96(35.7)	54(20.1)	11(4.1)	32(11.9)	76(28.3)	3.23	1.68
Online Cheating: Using the internet to cheat on tests, quizzes, or assignments	43(16)	97(36.1)	52(19.3)	22(8.2)	55(20.4)	3.19	1.37
Online Gambling: Engaging in illegal or age-inappropriate gambling activities online	54(20.1)	64(23.8)	43(16)	65(24.2)	43(16)	3.08	1.39
Cyberbullying: Being mean or spreading rumours about someone online	43(16)	85(31.6)	43(16)	10(3.7)	88(32.7)	2.94	1.52
Examination questions leakage	52(19.3)	76(28.3)	43(16)	-	98(36.4)	2.94	1.59
Pornography: Sharing or looking at inappropriate pictures or videos online	33(12.3)	53(19.7)	53(19.7)	87(32.3)	43(16)	2.80	1.27
Harassment and Stalking: Constantly bothering someone online or following their every move	11(4.1)	106(39.4)	43(16)	21(7.8)	88(32.7)	2.74	1.37
Spread of Misinformation: Sharing fake news or lies to trick people	11(4.1)	54(20.1)	95(35.3)	11(4.1)	98(36.4)	2.51	1.28
Digital Piracy: Illegally downloading or sharing copyrighted material, such as movies, music, or software.	11(4.1)	21(7.8)	87(32.3)	31(11.5)	119(44.2)	2.16	1.19
Hate Speech: Saying hurtful things about someone because of their race, religion, or other differences.	21(7.8)	22(8.2)	31(11.5)	75(27.9)	120(44.6)	2.07	1.26
Fraud and Scams: Tricking people into giving away their money or personal information online	-	21(7.8)	44(16.4)	64(23.8)	140(52)	1.80	0.98
Scam dating	-	10(3.7)	22(8.2)	107(39.8)	130(48.3)	1.67	0.78
Drug Trafficking: Selling or buying drugs through social media	11(4.1)	-	42(15.6)	22(8.2)	194(72.1)	1.56	1.03
Plagiarism: Copying and pasting content from the internet without proper citation or credit	-	21(7.8)	-	54(20.1)	194(72.1)	1.43	0.85
Identity Theft: Stealing someone's information to pretend to be them or steal their money	10(3.7)	11(4.1)	-	31(11.5)	217(80.7)	1.39	0.97
Hacking and Cyber Attacks: Breaking into computers or networks to steal information or cause damage	-	-	20(7.4)	32(11.9)	217(80.7)	1.27	0.59
Grand mean						2.45	1.22

Source: Field Survey, 2024

 \bar{x} = Mean, Std.d. = Standard Deviation. Figures in parenthesis are in percentage

Figure 5: Frequency of Use of Social Media

4.6 Test of Hypotheses

4.6.1 Hypothesis 1: "There is no significant association between the socio-personal characteristics of the respondents and criminal and deviant behaviour of the respondents"

Chi-square analysis was used to evaluate the hypothesis. Sex, age, class, religion, kind of home, size of household, yearly income, mothers' and dads' educational backgrounds, occupations, and class were among the personal traits taken into account. The significance of the correlation was assessed at a 5% level. The results of the Chi-square analysis are presented in Table 12 which shows a significant ($p < 0.05$)

association between the deviant behaviour and the class level ($\chi^2=23.32$, $df=6$), type of home ($\chi^2=31.18$, $df=2$), household size ($\chi^2=158.08$, $df=6$), annual income ($\chi^2=127.77$, $df=6$), mothers' education ($\chi^2=90.18$, $df=6$), fathers' occupation ($\chi^2=49.75$, $df=8$), mothers' occupation ($\chi^2=82.67$, $df=8$), and fathers' education ($\chi^2=84.63$, $df=10$).

The results in Table 12 also show that there is a significant ($p<0.05$) association between criminal behaviour and the following factors: age ($\chi^2=50.61$, $df=4$), class ($\chi^2=73.44$, $df=6$), type of home ($\chi^2=31.85$, $df=2$), household size ($\chi^2=96.54$, $df=6$), annual income ($\chi^2=88.54$, $df=6$), mothers' education ($\chi^2=112.48$, $df=6$), fathers' occupation ($\chi^2=99.71$, $df=8$) and mothers' occupation ($\chi^2=70.39$, $df=8$).

Table 12: Test of significant association between the socio-personal characteristics of the respondents and criminal and deviant behaviour of the respondents using Chi-square

Variables	Deviant Behaviour				Criminal Behaviour			
	χ^2	df	p-Value	Decision	χ^2	df	p-Value	Decision
Sex	5.52	2	0.06	NS	3.21	2	0.20	NS
Age	0.47	4	0.98	NS	50.61	4	0.00	S
Class	23.31	6	0.00	S	73.44	6	0.00	S
Religion	5.53	4	0.24	NS	2.95	4	0.57	NS
Type of home	31.18	2	0.00	S	31.85	2	0.00	S
Household size	158.08	6	0.00	S	96.54	6	0.00	S
Annual income	127.77	6	0.00	S	88.54	6	0.00	S
Fathers' education	84.63	10	0.00	S	69.73	10	0.00	S
Mothers' education	90.18	6	0.00	S	112.48	6	0.00	S
Fathers' occupation	49.75	8	0.00	S	99.71	8	0.00	S
Mothers' occupation	82.67	8	0.00	S	70.39	8	0.00	S

Source: Field Survey, 2024

NS = Not Significant

S = Significant

4.6.2 Hypothesis 2: Test of the relationship between the variables influencing criminal and behaviours and respondents' criminal and deviant behaviours

In Table 13, the hypothesis that "there is no significant relationship between the variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviours and respondents' criminal and deviant behaviour" was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). A significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation was found between the school environment ($r = 0.42$), parenting style ($r = 0.43$), peer pressure ($r = 0.55$), social media ($r = 0.50$), and deviant behaviour.

Furthermore, Table 13 revealed a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) between criminal behaviour and multiple factors, specifically school environment ($r = 0.57$), parenting style ($r = 0.33$), peer pressure ($r = 0.37$), and social media usage ($r = 0.40$).

Table 13: Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) testing for correlation between variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviours and respondents' criminal and deviant behaviours

Variables	School environment	Peer pressure	Parenting styles	Social media	Deviant behaviour	Criminal behaviour
School environment	-					
Peer pressure	0.31**	-				
Parenting styles	0.27**		-			
Social media	0.11	0.61**		-		
Deviant behaviour	0.42**	0.55**	0.43**	0.50**	-	
Criminal behaviour	0.57**	0.37**	0.33**	0.40**	0.75**	-

Source: Field Survey, 2024

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.6.3. Hypothesis 3: Test of the significant contribution by the overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviour of respondents

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was used to test the hypothesis that "there is no significant contribution by overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents." Result findings are presented in Table 14, which indicates that a significantly negative correlation ($p < 0.05$) occurs between deviant conduct and sex ($\beta = -0.09$), age ($\beta = -0.22$), religion ($\beta = -0.15$), style of home ($\beta = -0.35$), and household size ($\beta = -0.19$). In contrast, annual income ($\beta = 0.75$), school environment ($\beta = 0.49$) and social media ($\beta = 0.27$) showed significant positive correlations. 77% (R square = 0.77) of the variance in deviant conduct can be attributed to these independent variables.

Criminal behaviour was influenced by several factors, including religion ($\beta = -0.15$), type of home ($\beta = -0.42$), household size ($\beta = -0.24$), annual income ($\beta = 0.38$), fathers' education ($\beta = -0.20$), mothers' education ($\beta = 0.17$), fathers' occupation ($\beta = 0.38$), mothers' occupation ($\beta = -0.24$), school environment ($\beta = 0.56$), peer pressure ($\beta = -0.19$), and social media ($\beta = 0.47$) at a significance of $p < 0.05$. All things considered, 72% (R square = 0.72) of criminal behaviour may be attributed to the independent variables.

Table 14: Test of a significant contribution by the overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents

Variables	Deviant Behaviour					Criminal Behaviour				
	B	Std. E.	t-Value	Sig.	Decision	B	Std. E.	t-Value	Sig.	Decision
(Constant)	-42.36	9.14	-4.64	0.00		46.46	8.05	-5.78	0.00	
Sex	-0.09	0.98	-2.19	0.03	S	0.05	0.86	1.08	0.28	NS
Age	-0.22	0.79	-4.96	0.00	S	-0.03	0.69	-0.56	0.57	NS
Class	-0.04	0.43	-0.97	0.33	NS	-0.01	0.38	-0.27	0.79	NS
Religion	-0.15	0.92	-3.72	0.00	S	-0.15	0.81	-3.47	0.00	S
Type of home	-0.35	1.26	-7.08	0.00	S	-0.42	1.11	-7.76	0.00	S
Household size	-0.19	0.30	-3.30	0.00	S	-0.24	0.27	-3.89	0.00	S
Annual income	0.75	0.68	14.59	0.00	S	0.38	0.60	6.74	0.00	S
Fathers' education	-0.03	0.46	-0.64	0.52	NS	-0.20	0.41	-3.42	0.00	S
Mothers' education	0.00	0.80	0.06	0.95	NS	0.17	0.70	2.36	0.02	S
Fathers' occupation	0.06	0.60	0.96	0.34	NS	0.38	0.53	5.86	0.00	S
Mothers' occupation	0.03	0.66	0.51	0.61	NS	-0.24	0.58	-3.32	0.00	S
School environment	0.49	0.13	10.97	0.00	S	0.56	0.12	11.38	0.00	S
Parenting styles	0.23	0.53	4.32	0.00	S	0.68	0.23	8.98	0.00	S
Peer pressure	0.02	0.03	0.39	0.70	NS	-0.19	0.03	-2.96	0.00	S
Social media	0.27	0.05	4.87	0.00	S	0.47	0.04	7.79	0.00	S
R²	0.77					0.72				
Adjusted R²	0.76					0.71				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

NS = Not Significant

S = Significant

4.6.4 Hypothesis 4: Test of significant difference in the criminal and deviant behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents

The results of the test comparing the deviant and criminal behaviour displayed by male and female respondents are presented in Table 15. The findings indicate that there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in deviant behaviours exhibited by male ($\bar{x} = 42.55$) and female ($\bar{x} = 38.44$) respondents ($t = 2.96$). This suggests that there are gender differences in the deviant behaviour displayed by male and female.

But when it came to the criminal behaviour displayed by male and female respondents, there was no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) ($t = 0.10$).

Table 15: Test of significant differences in the criminal and deviant behaviour exhibited by male and female respondents

Variables	Sex	N	Mean	Std. D	df	Std. E	t-Value	p-Value	Decision
Deviant behaviour	Male	129	42.55	12.20	267	1.07	2.96	0.00	S
	Female	140	38.14	12.19	265.19	1.03			
Criminal behaviour	Male	129	31.22	8.67	267	0.76	0.10	0.92	NS
	Female	140	31.11	10.94	261.26	0.92			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

NS = Not Significant

S = Significant

4.7 Discussion

The result in Table 3 shows the demographic characteristics of respondents where the majority (52.0%) were female, in line with secondary school enrolment statistics from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (2016–2017) that indicates a higher percentage of female students attended public secondary schools in Lagos State. In terms of age distribution, 52.0% of the respondents were between the ages of 16 - 18. Age differences can affect a person's susceptibility to peer pressure and risky behaviour. For example, older teens may be more exposed to peer pressure related to substance abuse, delinquency, and risky behaviour than younger peers, this research findings about age range's susceptibility to these behaviours are supported by a previous study by Deepika & Prema (2017).

Regarding school categorisation, SSS3 accounted for the largest number (35.7%), with SSS2 coming in second at 28.6%. Teenagers in SSS3 and SSS2 may feel more pressure and stress because of upcoming exams and future changes (career and life choices, increased responsibilities and personal aspirations).

Contrary to Ostien's (2012) findings, which attribute Lagos State's religious composition mostly to Muslims, this study's religious distribution revealed that the majority of respondents (61.7%) were Christians.

Family structure revealed that a higher percentage of participants (63.9%) were from monogamous households. Because monogamous families provide sufficient supervision and monitoring, there may be fewer conflicting demands on parents' time and resources, which could affect the degree of parental involvement in their kids' schooling. While earlier research (Craig & Glick, 2012; Kumi, 2015; Ferdinand, 2010 cited in Peter & Nwadukwe, 2022; Bello, 2023) discussed the role of single-home and

polygamous family structures in contributing to teenage deviant behaviours, no prior academic studies were found to address the question of whether or not monogamous family structures contributed to teenage crimes and deviant behaviour because this particular type of family structure influence has not yet been thoroughly studied in Nigeria or Africa.

Nigeria's average household size in urban areas is 4.5, according to a report from the National Population Commission and International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (2019). On the contrary, the major household size for this study ranged between 4 - 6 persons with an average of 5.73 (~ 6).

In line with the UNDP-OPHI report (2022), which estimates that 39.1% of Nigerians live on less than US\$1.90, the annual income distribution of respondents' parents showed that the largest proportion (39.8%) earned between 500,000 - 2,000,000, followed by 2,000,000 - 5,000,000 (27.9%), below 500,000 (20.4%), and above 5,000,000 (11.9%).

Maternal education comprised HND/BSc, ND/NCE, SSCE, and Postgraduate certificate while Fathers' education varied from Postgraduate certificate (23.8%) to no formal education (7.8%). Fathers' occupations ranged from private workers at the highest to unemployed people at the lowest; notably, mothers' occupations were predominantly in trading and business. Parenting methods, communication techniques, and level of involvement in their kids' lives can all be influenced by their educational background. Being exposed to a variety of professional settings through their parents' jobs may increase teenagers' awareness of potential career paths and opportunities, which in turn lowers the likelihood that they will engage in deviant and criminal behaviour. Teenagers from such households where parents have higher

educational attainment may also exhibit higher educational aspirations and achievement.

The occupations that parents hold impact family dynamics, financial stability, and parental involvement. Occupations with high-stress levels or irregular hours restrict parental assistance and supervision; however, jobs with steady employment and parental involvement allow for positive role modelling and supervision. Because financial stability reduces stress related to basic needs like food, shelter, and healthcare, and will enable teenagers to focus more on the future, higher-income households may provide their teenagers with better educational resources, such as educational technology, opportunities, support systems enrichment programs, and private tutoring. A teenager's tendency to deviant and criminal activity may be increased by socioeconomic difficulties, limited access to extracurricular and educational activities, and exposure to neighbourhood influences. This study's finding that a family's socioeconomic status may contribute to a teen's engagement in criminal and deviant behaviours is corroborated by earlier research by Aute *et al.*, (2020); Nezhad, *et al.*, (2012); Uyang *et al.*, (2016); Owusu, (2016) and Sharkey, *et al.*, (2017).

The majority of respondents displayed moderately deviant behaviours, with the most common deviant behaviours among them being lying to adults, petty theft, and making threats or insults online. Substance abuse and getting into fights on the street or in gangs were less common among the respondents.

Having criminal friends who are well-known to the police, knowing multiple people who have committed crimes, and being accepted by their criminal friends were common criminal behaviours displayed by the respondents. On the other hand, having

criminal friends, stealing, and holding it against anyone were rated poorly, with average means of 2.08 and 2.23, respectively.

The school environment and parenting styles were the primary factors leading to deviant and criminal behaviour closely followed by peer pressure and the use of social media. Teenage behaviour is greatly shaped by their school environment, which also affects their propensity to commit crimes or engage in deviant activity. Various factors within the school environment such as overcrowding, lack of resources, unfair treatment, bullying, dilapidated school buildings, pressure to perform well academically, boredom, violent acts within the school environment and inadequate support from teachers and peers have been found to have the potential to influence teenagers to conform to deviant behaviours to fit in or gain acceptance among peers as a coping strategy, to take control of their surroundings, cope with academic demands or to express themselves.

Furthermore, beliefs that those in positions of authority were treating them unfairly can undermine respect for the law and incite disobedience or resistance through unconventional action. When schools don't offer pleasant extracurricular activities, pupils may be unintentionally encouraged to engage in harmful behaviours. All this aligns with findings from previous studies by Stewart & Simons, (2010); Masitsa, (2011); Mbaabu & Orodho, (2014); Cheng, (2012); Khumalo, (2019) and Yaman & Uygumada (2009).

Parenting styles, such as authoritative and overprotective also played significant roles in shaping behaviours. Authoritative parenting - which is characterized by high expectations and high levels of responsiveness - style ranked highest among respondents, parental responses to mistakes tended to be critical rather than

supportive, and communicating problems to parents was difficult due to fear of their reactions. In line with previous studies by McNamara *et al.* (2010), Simons *et al.* (2007), and Hoskins (2014), authoritative parenting, which is characterised by a sense of obligation to adhere to parental rules, even when a disagreement arises, ranked highest among respondents.

The respondents' parents also tended to adopt an overly protective parenting style, frequently reacting with fear or anger to their children's attempts at independence. Parents were criticised for exercising excessive control over their children, preventing them from making their own decisions and growing from them. The self-reliance of the respondents was hampered by constant parental supervision and intervention. In contrast, students' autonomy and self-regulation may be hampered by overprotective parenting, which is characterised by excessive control and intrusiveness. These teenagers could have trouble making decisions, solving problems, and handling difficulties on their own.

The Neglectful parenting style which is low on responsiveness and demandingness was the third-rated parenting style identified in this study. Respondents experience feelings of insecurity and abandonment as a result of their parent's lack of involvement in their lives; they believe that their parents don't care about their problems or how they are feeling. Children who feel abandoned and alone due to their parents' frequent absences or preoccupation with their own lives may find themselves on their own at times, lacking the support and direction they require.

Permissive parents are quick to respond to their children's needs without placing any demands on them which could lead to children turning outside the home for answers. A feeling of parents prioritizing being friends with their children over parenting leaves their teenagers confused and feeling unsupported, parents being too lenient, not setting clear boundaries, and not taking responsibilities for their children seriously enough could make a child prone to deviant behaviours. Parents who refuse to provide guidance and structure to their wards leaving them to figure life out on their own or refusing to enforce consequences for wrong actions or behaviours are risk factors to criminal and deviant behaviour.

Research by Maccoby & Martins, (1983); Baumrind, Larzelere, & Owens (quoted in Hoskins, 2014); Simons *et al.*, (2007); Johnson, (2016); Utti, (2006); Menkiti, (2019); and Hoeve *et al.*, (2009) support the findings of this study, which show that teenagers' criminal behaviour and deviant behaviour are related to how demanding and responsive the parenting principles adopted by parents are.

Peer influence and social media interactions further worsened deviant and criminal tendencies, with respondents succumbing to the influence and engaging in risky behaviours. Regarding the influence of peers, the respondents mentioned situations in which they had lied to parents or authorities in order to get out of trouble, with the substance abuse of their friends having an impact on their actions. They also skipped class when their classmates did, engaged in dangerous activity when friends dared them to, and occasionally showed disrespect for their parents when they were upset. It has been seen that friends will put pressure on one another to partake in unhealthy habits, such as drinking or smoking to fit in and accept friends' opinions even when

they are uncomfortable. Rape and engagement in cult activities, however, were not often reported by the interviewees.

Teenagers' need to belong may cause them to embrace behaviours or attitudes that their peer group supports, even when those actions go against their values or beliefs. The need to fit in frequently forces teens to comply with group norms and expectations in order to win acceptance and approval. Teens who seek to fit in with their peers' expectations may continue to engage in deviant actions as a result of this conformity. Studies by Kurtz & Zavala, (2017); Arief & Martins, (2011); Kim *et al.*, (2010); Ajayi & Ekundayo, (2010); Deepika & Prema, (2017) support the role played by deviant peers, how peer pressure could be employed, and how it leads to criminal and deviant behaviour found throughout this study.

Similarly, excessive social media or gaming consumption was noted as resulting in neglect of responsibilities and relationships. Additionally, sharing sexually explicit content without consent and posting mean or offensive comments were common behaviours. Some respondents admitted to using the internet to cheat on assessments and engaging in illegal gambling activities online. Spreading rumours and sharing inappropriate content were also reported. However, stealing personal information to impersonate or steal money, as well as breaking into computers or networks for malicious purposes, were minimally reported. Excessive social media or gaming consumption can lead to neglect of academic responsibilities, developing an aggressive behaviour toward other people, household chores and other obligations. Students may prioritize online activities over schoolwork, leading to decreased academic performance and strained relationships with family and peers. Some students may resort to using the internet to cheat in assessments or engage in illegal

gambling activities online. These behaviours compromise academic integrity and can result in disciplinary actions, academic sanctions and long-term consequences for students' educational and career prospects. Students may engage in sharing sexually explicit content without consent or posting mean, offensive comments online. These behaviours can contribute to cyberbullying, harm relationships and have legal consequences. Social media platforms can be breeding grounds for the spread of rumours and misinformation. Students may unknowingly contribute to the dissemination of false information, which can have negative societal impacts and perpetuate harmful stereotypes.

Furthermore, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube and Twitter emerged as the primary social media platforms among secondary school students, indicating widespread usage and popularity. Conversely, platforms like Tumblr and Discord received lower ratings, suggesting less engagement and relevance among the student population.

Additionally, school environments, peer pressure and social media had correlations with deviant and criminal behaviours, emphasizing their influential roles. The school environment, including the culture, disciplinary policies and quality of relationship between students and staff can influence a students' behaviour. A positive school climate characterized by supportive relationships, clear expectations and opportunities for involvement in extracurricular activities can reduce the likelihood of deviant and criminal behaviours which is supported by the works of Johnson, *et al.*, (2015) which says that a healthy school environment builds positive relationships that can keep teenagers away from crimes. Conversely, a negative or unsafe school environment may compound risk factors and contribute to students engaging in delinquent

activities. This is corroborated by Bradshaw *et al.*, (2015) who reported in their study that an unsupportive school environment breeds criminal behaviour among high school students. Similarly, Laurito *et al.*, (2019) reported in their study that school climate has a way of influencing criminal tendencies and behaviour of adolescents.

This is consistent with the research by Xiong *et al.*, (2020) regarding the impact of parenting styles on juvenile delinquency in Chinese teenagers. It was shown that criminal behaviour was significantly predicted by parenting styles that were both permissive and authoritative.

Adolescent behaviour, especially deviant and criminal behaviour, is greatly influenced by their peers. Peer pressure to follow social standards, take risks, or partake in criminal activities can all be significant predictors of teenage delinquency. Teenagers who are looking for excitement and novelty, fearing rejection, or want acceptability may give in to peer pressure (Monahan, et al., 2020). The findings of a previous study by Kim & Fletcher (2019) are in line with the results of this study where peer pressure was found to have a significant relationship with criminal and deviant behaviour based on the differential association theory by Sutherland in (1947) which explained that friends shape each other's behaviour primarily through exchange of values, social reinforcement and behavioural modelling. Because teenagers are immature, the negative impact of others can cause them to engage in criminal behaviours, teenagers who keep criminal friends will learn criminal behaviours by observing and imitating what their friends do to be accepted in the group which means that teenagers who are pressured by their peers will most likely be involved in criminal behaviour. Based on this theory and the research

findings, it is safe to say that peer pressure contributes to deviant and criminal behaviour.

Social media platforms provide adolescents with opportunities for social interaction, self-expression and information sharing. However, excessive use of social media and exposure to harmful content can contribute to deviant and criminal behaviours. Cyberbullying, online harassment, sharing inappropriate content and engaging in illegal activities through social media platforms are prevalent concerns among adolescents. Moreover, social media platforms may facilitate peer pressure and exposure to deviant peer networks, further influencing adolescents' behaviours. This finding corroborates the study by Moro, *et al.*, (2022) which found that there is a significant and positive link between social media use and criminal behaviour

Chi-square analysis for hypothesis one found significant association ($p < 0.05$) between deviant behaviours and class level, type of home, household size, annual income of parents, mothers' education, mothers' occupation, fathers' occupation and fathers' education. Also, age, class, type of home, household size, annual income of parents, fathers' education, mothers' education, fathers' occupation and mothers' occupation was found to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated with criminal behaviours.

Therefore, the hypothesis – that there is no significant relationship between socio-personal characteristics of respondents and crimes and deviant behaviours of respondents – is rejected, with inference drawn that there is a significant association between socio-personal characteristics of the respondents and criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents.

Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation in analysing hypothesis two, results from Table 11 show that there are significant relationships between school environment ($r = 0.42$), peer pressure ($r = 0.55$), parental style ($r = 0.43$), social media usage ($r = 0.50$) and deviant behaviour. It also showed that school environment ($r = 0.57$), parental style ($r = 0.33$), peer influence ($r = 0.37$), social media ($r = 0.40$) had significant relationships with criminal behaviours. Consequently, the hypothesis—that there is no significant relationship between the variables influencing criminal and deviant behaviour and respondents' criminal and deviant behaviours—is rejected.

Hypothesis three was analysed using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS). Results show that independent variables contributed 72% ($R^2 = 0.72$) and 77% ($R^2 = 0.77$) to criminal and deviant behaviour respectively. The hypothesis - that there is no significant relationship contribution by the overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents - is rejected, accepting the alternate hypothesis that there is a significant contribution by overall independent variables to criminal and deviant behaviours of the respondents.

Using Student - t test to analyse hypothesis four, results indicated a significant ($p = 0.05$) difference in deviant behaviours exhibited by male teenagers ($\bar{x} = 42.55$) and female ($\bar{x} = 38.14$) respondents with male respondents having a higher score of $t = 2.96$ while there was no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in criminal behaviours $t = 0.10$ exhibited by male and female respondents. The hypothesis - there is no significant difference in the criminal and deviant behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents - will be accepted for criminal behaviour because there is no significant difference in the criminal behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents while the hypothesis will be rejected for deviant behaviour as it has

shown that there is significant difference in the deviant behaviours exhibited by male and female respondents.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The study examined the factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviours of teenagers in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government, Lagos State Nigeria. A multistage sampling procedure was used to select 269 respondents. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain data from the respondents and analysed using means, frequency, percentages, standard deviation, Chi-square, PPMC, OLS and Student t-test.

Majority of the respondents were female, age ranked majorly between 16-18 years old, and most were from monogamous families with 4 - 6 persons. Parents of most of the respondents earned between ₦500,000 - ₦2,000,000 annually, a higher proportion of fathers and mothers possess HND/BSc certificates, fathers were majorly private workers while mothers were majorly into trading/business.

More than half of the population of respondents used in the study (teenagers in public secondary schools) were observed to exhibit moderate levels of deviant behaviours with lying to adults ($\bar{x} = 3.71$) and engaging in petty theft ($\bar{x} = 3.38$) being the most prevalent. Although being friends with criminals well known by the police ($\bar{x} = 3.67$) and knowing several people who have committed crimes ($\bar{x} = 3.64$) were ranked high, most respondents were considered to exhibit moderate criminal behaviour.

School environment and parenting styles were determined to be the major factors contributing to crimes and deviant behaviours among the respondents. Chi-square analysis results revealed that a significant association exist between the socio-personal characteristics of the respondents and criminal and deviant behaviours of respondents.

PPMC revealed a significant relationship between school environment ($r = 0.42$), peer influence ($r = 0.55$), social media ($r = 0.50$) and deviant behaviour. It also showed a significant relationship between school environment ($r = 0.57$), peer influence ($r = 0.37$), social media ($r = 0.40$) and criminal behaviour. Overall independent variables contributed 77% and 72% to deviant and criminal behaviours respectively.

Student t-test showed that there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in deviant behaviour exhibited by male and female respondents ($t = 2.96$) with males involved in more deviant behaviours. Majority of the respondents exhibit a moderate level of criminal and deviant behaviours based on the categorisation of criminal and deviant behaviours into high (3.68 – 5.00), moderate (2.34 – 3.67) and low (1.00 -2.33) to determine the level of deviance among respondents.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study shed light on the prevalence and factors associated with deviant and criminal behaviours among respondents in public secondary schools in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State. Slightly more than half of the respondents demonstrated a moderate level of deviant behaviours, with lying to adults and engaging in petty theft being the most common manifestations. Moreover, a significant proportion exhibited moderate levels of criminal behaviours, including associating with known criminals and being acquainted with individuals involved in criminal activities.

The study identified school environment and parenting styles as significant contributors to both deviant and criminal behaviours among respondents, highlighting issues such as overpopulation in classrooms and the impact of strict parental rules. Additionally, the frequent use of social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and

TikTok was observed among respondents, suggesting a potential influence on their behaviours. In conclusion, peer pressure, school environment and social media usage are predictors of deviant and criminal behaviours.

Overall, these findings underscore the complex interplay of individual, familial and societal factors in shaping deviant or criminal behaviours among adolescents. Addressing these behaviours requires a multifaceted approach that considers not only individual characteristics but also broader social and environmental contexts. Further research and targeted interventions are warranted to mitigate the prevalence and impact of such behaviours on individuals and communities.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, several recommendations can be made to address the prevalence of deviant and criminal behaviours among adolescents:

- 1) Schools and policymakers in the education system should focus on improving the learning environment by addressing issues such as classroom overpopulation, dilapidated infrastructures, lack of educational resources bullying and unnecessary competition in the classroom. Teachers should be well-enumerated and encouraged to give the utmost performance and attention to their students.
- 2) Seminars, programs and jingles to teach parents about different parenting practices, how to identify the practice they employ, merits and demerits of each parenting practice and its future implications on their children should be regularly organized by schools, government and policymakers.

- 3) Parents should encourage open dialogue with their children, and promote mental positivity, self-discovery and assertiveness thereby reducing the need to seek affirmation, approval or acceptance from peers.
- 4) Educating adolescents about responsible social media usage and its potential impact on behaviour is crucial. Parents, schools and everyone in place of authority should work together to teach digital literacy skills and promote healthy online habits. Monitoring and limiting access to certain social media platforms may also be necessary to mitigate negative influences.
- 5) While not neglecting the girl child, specific and targeted career opportunities, mentorship and amenities for extracurricular activities should be provided for the boy child by parents, school authorities, policymakers and the government.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study intends to contribute to existing body of knowledge on crimes and deviant behaviours of teenagers by:

- 1) Providing an understanding to deviance in Nigerian schools by examining the factors contributing to these behaviours, and offering insights into challenges faced by these population.
- 2) Explaining how individuals (peer pressure, social media usage), family (income, parenting styles), and environmental (school environment) factors intersect and influence adolescent behaviours thus drawing on and extending theoretical frameworks.
- 3) Highlighting the need for comprehensive interventions that address the root cause of deviance among teenagers by the government and policymakers.

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APPENDIX

**FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE ABEOKUTA
COLLEGE OF FOOD TECHNOLOGY AND HUMAN ECOLOGY
DEPARTMENT OF HOME SCIENCE AND MANAGEMENT
(HUMAN DEVELOPMENT AND FAMILY STUDIES)**

Dear respondent,

I am a postgraduate student of Human Development and Family Studies option in the Department of Home Science and Management, Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta. My research topic is **“FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO CRIMES AND DEVIANT BEHAVIORS AMONG TEENAGERS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN**

ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT, LAGOS STATE NIGERIA”. This is the data gathering stage of the program and you are in the sampling frame of this study. Your assistance is being solicited by responding to the content of this questionnaire sincerely and honestly. I promise that all information given in this questionnaire shall be treated confidentially and will be used only as an academic exercise. Thank you in anticipation.

ABE O, ABIOLA

Informed Consent: I hereby agree to participate in this survey: Yes (), No ().

SECTION A: Demographic information

1. Sex: Male () Female ()
2. Age: 13 - 15 years () 16 - 18 years () 19 years and above ()
3. Class: JSS 3 (), SSS1 (), SSS2 (), SSS3 ()
4. Religion: Christianity () Islam () Traditional religion () No religion ()
5. Type of Home: Polygamous (), Monogamous () Single parent ()

SECTION B: Socio-economic information

6. Total household size (persons): _____
7. Family Income (per annum): Less than 500,000naira () 500,000naira – 2,000,000naira () 2,000,000naira – 5,000,000naira () More than 5,000,000naira ()
8. Father educational level: No formal education () Primary () SSCE () ND/NCE () HND/University degree () Postgraduate () Others (specify)_____
9. Mother educational level: No formal education () Primary () SSCE () ND/NCE () HND/University degree () Postgraduate () Others (specify)_____
10. Father occupation: Civil servant () Artisans () Trader/Business () Private () Unemployed ()

11. Mother occupation: Civil servant () Artisans () Trader/Business () Private ()
Unemployed ()

SECTION C: Deviant behaviours

Instruction: Kindly respond to the following questions as they apply to you. How often do you engage in the following behaviours?

SN	During the last year, have you ever....	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	Do you drink alcohol?					
2	Do you Lie to adults (e.g., family members, teachers, etc.)?					
3	Do you take substance abuse?					
4	How often do you have sex with multiple sex partners?					
5	How often do you hit anybody (e.g., students, siblings, teacher, family, security guard, etc.)?					
6	How regularly do you attend a cult meeting?					
7	How often do you vandalize any property?					
8	Do you rape or have been raped?					
9	How often have you engaged in petty theft?					
10	How often have you been involved in armed robbery?					
11	How often do you skip classes because you didn't felt like going, to stay with colleagues, or to go for a ride?					
	Items	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
12	When do you get involved in street or gang fight?					
13	How often do you engage in betting or sport betting?					
14	How often do you carry a weapon (e.g., knife, pistol, etc.)?					
15	Do you insult or threaten anyone online?					

SECTION D: Criminal behaviour

Instruction: Kindly respond to the following questions as they apply to you. How often do you engage in the following behaviours?

SN	Questions	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	Stealing and holding it against anyone					
2	Sense of kinship with law breakers.					
3	Lack of respect for authority.					
4	Have criminal friends.					

5	None of my friends have committed crimes					
6	None of my friends has ever wanted to commit a crime.					
7	I know several people who have committed crimes					
8	Criminal friends who are well known to the police					
9	Committed a crime before.					
10	Most of my friends don't have criminal records.					
11	I am accepted by my criminal friends.					

SECTION F: Parenting style

Instruction: Please respond to the following statements as they occur to you.

SN	ITEMS	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
	Authoritarian Parenting					
1.	My parents often punish me without explaining why, making me feel frustrated and confused					
2.	I feel like I have to obey my parents' rules all the time, even if I don't agree with them					
3.	When I make a mistake, my parents tend to be harsh and critical rather than understanding and supportive					
4.	I find it difficult to talk to my parents about my problems because I'm afraid of their reactions					
	Permissive Parenting					
5.	My parents rarely set boundaries or enforce consequences for my actions, leading me to feel unsure of where the limits are					
6.	I feel like my parents prioritize being my friend over being my parent, which can be confusing and leave me feeling unsupported					
7.	Sometimes, I wish my parents would provide more guidance and structure in my life instead of letting me figure things out on my own					
8.	I often feel like my parents are too lenient and don't take my responsibilities seriously enough					
	Neglectful Parenting					

9.	My parents are often absent or preoccupied with their own lives, leaving me feeling neglected and alone					
	ITEMS	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
10.	I don't feel like my parents are interested in what's going on in my life or how I'm feeling					
11.	I sometimes have to fend for myself because my parents aren't around to provide the support and guidance I need					
12.	I struggle with feelings of abandonment and insecurity because of my parents' lack of involvement in my life					
	Overprotective Parenting					
13.	My parents are overly controlling and don't give me the freedom to make my own choices or learn from my mistakes					
14.	I feel suffocated by my parents' constant monitoring and interference in my life, making it hard for me to develop independence					
15.	When I try to assert my independence, my parents react with fear or anger, which makes me hesitant to express myself					
16.	I worry that my parents' overprotectiveness is hindering my ability to develop important life skills and cope with challenges on my own					

SECTION G: School environment

Instruction: Kindly respond to the following questions as they apply to you. Use the following keys; SD - Strongly Disagree, D - Disagree, U - Undecided, A - Agree, SA - Strongly Agree

SN	Questions	SD	D	U	A	SA
1.	Classes are received in dilapidated buildings					
2.	There is overpopulation of students in a class					
3.	I have felt bullied or harassed by other students or teachers at school					
4.	Sometimes, I feel like my teachers don't understand or care about my needs					
5.	There is too much pressure to do well academically at school					
6.	I often feel stressed or overwhelmed by schoolwork					

7.	I have felt bored or uninterested in what I'm learning at school					
8.	There aren't enough textbooks and materials for me to use at school					
9.	The school lacks enough technology and resources to support my learning					
10.	I have witnessed or experienced violence or threats at school					
11.	Not everyone at school is treated fairly and equally					
12.	I find it challenging to make friends and get along with other students at school					
13.	I have felt isolated or left out by my classmates					
14.	The school doesn't provide enough opportunities for me to grow and develop outside of academics					
15.	There aren't enough extracurricular activities and programs available for me to participate in at school					
16.	There aren't enough resources (e.g. counselling) available at school to help students with mental health issues					

SECTION H: Peer pressure

Instructions: Please respond to the following statements as they occur to you.

SN	ITEMS	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
	Direct Influence					
1.	I have felt pressured by my friends to do things I didn't want to do					
2.	My friends often convince me to go along with their ideas even if I'm not comfortable.					
3.	I've found myself doing things I disagree with because my friends thought it was cool.					
	Risk-taking Behaviour					
4.	I've taken risks or done dangerous things because my friends dared me to.					
5.	When my friends are around, I'm more likely to try things I wouldn't normally try.					
6.	I've been involved in cult activities					
	Substance Use					
7.	Sometimes I feel like I have to drink or smoke to be accepted by my friends.					
8.	My friends' use of drugs or alcohol makes me more likely to use them too.					
	Social Acceptance					
9.	My friends have made me feel like I'm not cool if I don't do what they do.					
10.	I've pretended to like something just to fit in with my friends.					

11.	I've avoided doing things I enjoy because my friends wouldn't approve.					
	Absenteeism					
12.	I have skipped class because my friends were skipping					
13.	I skip class more often when my friends aren't attending.					
	Sexual Involvement					
14.	I have been involved in sexual activities because I thought it would make me more popular.					
15.	I have witnessed or heard about instances of sexual assault or rape in my social circle.					
16.	I and my friends have been involved in raping					
	Disrespect for Elderly					
17.	I sometimes talk back or disrespect my parents when I'm angry or upset.					
18.	I've lied to parents or authorities on where I am or what I'm doing to avoid getting in trouble.					
19.	I sometimes feel like I don't need to follow the rules set by authorities because they don't understand my perspective.					

SECTION I: Social Media Usage

How regularly do you visit each social media page?

SN	Items	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	Facebook					
2	Twitter					
4	Instagram					
8	TikTok					
9	Tumblr					
10	Snapchat					
11	YouTube					
12	Telegram					
13	Discord					
14	Tinder					

Instructions: Please respond to the following statements as they occur to you. How often do you engage in the following behaviours?

SN	Items	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	Cyberbullying: Being mean or spreading rumours about someone					

	online					
2	Trolling: Trying to make others upset by posting mean or offensive comments					
4	Harassment and Stalking: Constantly bothering someone online or following their every move					
8	Hate Speech: Saying hurtful things about someone because of their race, religion, or other differences.					
9	Spread of Misinformation: Sharing fake news or lies to trick people					
10	Identity Theft: Stealing someone's information to pretend to be them or steal their money					
11	Fraud and Scams: Tricking people into giving away their money or personal information online					
12	Drug Trafficking: Selling or buying drugs through social media					
13	Hacking and Cyber Attacks: Breaking into computers or networks to steal information or cause damage					
14	Pornography: Sharing or looking at inappropriate pictures or videos online					
15	Scam dating					
16	Examination questions leakage					
17.	Sexting: Sharing sexually explicit messages, photos, or videos with peers, often without consent.					
18.	Excessive Screen Time: Spending too much time on social media or gaming, leading to neglect of responsibilities or relationships.					
19.	Plagiarism: Copying and pasting content from the internet without proper citation or credit					
20.	Online Gambling: Engaging in illegal or age inappropriate gambling activities online					
21.	Digital Piracy: Illegally downloading or sharing copyrighted material, such as movies, music, or software.					
22.	Online Cheating: Using the internet to cheat on tests, quizzes, or					

	assignments					
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